

Content Analysis of Most Transformative Visions

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	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Circular Economics (ID = 15, 28, 29, 33, 34, 38, 46, 47, 48, 60, 63, 65, 70)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	To envision a different economy based on circularity that restores and regenerates the Earth and yet it is appealing to the business sector and to policymakers.
The 'What'	Economic systems are designed to be restorative and regenerative, use renewable energy, avoids toxic products, extend the life cycle of products, turn old products, and wastes into new inputs for the economy through repair and recycling. It applies to industry, agriculture (food) and mobility. By maximizing the productivity of already circulating materials, the demand for raw materials and the economic throughput are reduced. The recycling and reprocessing of goods and materials generates jobs, saves resources and energy, and reduces waste. Social wealth (understood as natural, cultural, human, and manufactured stocks) rises. Re-circulating products and materials leaves more room for nature and biodiversity in land, ocean, and freshwater. Nature is actively employed to regenerate natural systems.
Broad Values	Stewardship, prosumerism, (re-)circularity, (economic) growth
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Circularity is meant to reduce the demand for raw materials and to leaving more room to nature. This speaks to an intrinsic value. However, the vision is largely and mostly instrumental. Nature is also actively employed to regenerate natural systems, an interesting combination of instrumental and intrinsic value. Instead, the relational component does not seem to be present in the vision description.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Land-use change and sea use</i>: It reduces the amount of land and marine resources needed to provide resources to the economy. ● <i>Natural resource use and exploitation</i>: It manages renewable resources (e.g. fish stocks) for the long term. ● <i>Climate change</i>: It reduces greenhouse gas emissions across the economy. ● <i>Pollution</i>: It designs out pollution at every stage of a product's life cycle. ● <i>Invasive species</i>: It designs out the waste on which invasive alien species can be transported to new ecosystems.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Economic</i>: A change in the way the economic system is designed/implemented leaves more space to nature and biodiversity. Considerably different production processes. Besides what has been said under the 'What', businesses are encouraged to assess biodiversity impacts, identify circular economy opportunities to meet biodiversity targets, and collaborate across value chains to develop innovative solutions aimed at systemic change. Does not question the growth ideal. ● <i>Governance</i>: Not a lot of reference to governance systems, although the reference to stewardship instead of ownership and other economic characteristics of the envisioned economic system have clear implications for governance. For example, it implies considerably different supporting structures for businesses, relevant support from policy/governments and shifted metrics. New structures, values, and

	<p>policy need to be developed to support circularity instead of take-make-waste processes. New regulations would be needed that emphasize metrics stressing the extent to which raw materials are reprocessed, and shifts away from fostering ownership of goods towards leasing and shared business models need to be developed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● <i>Technological</i>: More or less explicit reliance on renewable energy sources and technologies to recycle/retrofit materials.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Degrowth and Steady State (ID = 23, 61, 62, 64, 65, 67, 68, 73)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	To downscale and stabilize the size of the economic system in order to improve ecological conditions and wellbeing.
The 'What'	A downscaled economic system in the Global North allows to approximate a globally equitable steady state economy where the Global South has more autonomy to decide its own path to wellbeing. The downscaling and subsequent stabilization of the economy is socially sustainable and improves the state of nature. The key is a downscaling of throughput, meaning the materials and energy a society extracts, processes, consumes and returns back to the environment as waste. Focus on the meaning of life and the economics of happiness. The society has liberated from the drive to consume and produce and is instead focused on principles of sufficiency (see Broad Values). The new society reuses materials to satisfy needs, and sees as highly problematic wasteful consumption, extractivism and planned obsolescence. The new economy has constant stocks of physical wealth (artifacts) and a constant population that nature can support. For this, throughput is controlled from the extraction of low entropy resources to the production of high entropy waste. Laws of thermodynamics are taken into account in the design of the economic system. Inequality has been greatly reduced both within and between countries. The scale of the economy in resource throughput remains constant at a level that does not deplete/pollute the environment beyond its regenerative capacity. The economy is allowed to improve qualitatively by improving knowledge, organization, technical efficiency and wisdom. The economy delivers a high quality of life by focus on what really matters to people: health, wellbeing, employment, leisure time, strong communities and economic stability. People have equal opportunities to obtain wealth and income (fair distribution) and markets are harnessed to allocate resources among competing uses (efficient allocation). The new society does not believe in technology as the solution to all problems, but uses it to manage resources efficiently without the growth orientation of productive processes. Circular degrowth represents a vision of a socio-economic system that thrives in a symbiotic and regenerative relationship with the natural environment, where waste facilitates this relationship. Circularity occurs not only in material transactions with nature and social interactions but also at the level of the inner being of people.
Broad Values	Sufficiency. Autonomy. Democracy. Equality. Justice. Integration/harmony humans-nature. Ecology.
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Intrinsic</i>: Core principles of both approaches emphasize ecology, that is a belief that ecosystems have value in themselves, not just for the services they provide to humans. Paths to preserve and regenerate ecosystems are discussed. ● <i>Relational</i>: Can be inferred from this vision emphasis on autonomy and conviviality. ● <i>Instrumental</i>: Although nature is used in the economic system, given anti-utilitarian perspective of at least the degrowth proposal, this

	value seems to be of less importance, although perhaps a bit more in the steady-state.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	The downscaling and stabilization of the economic system, as well as the principle of "Reduction, recycling and reuse" has implications for all direct drivers of biodiversity loss, although they are not mentioned in the vision.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Demographic</i>: Steady-state speaks about the optimal size of the economic system which is defined as per capita throughput times population. Degrowth defends demographic stabilization through voluntary reductions in fertility facilitated by empowered women (although not mentioned in the vision). Thus they both address this indirect driver. ● <i>Economic</i>: The economic changes (downscaling and stabilization of throughput and related changes) directly tackle the indirect economic drivers of biodiversity loss. ● <i>Governance</i>: Implementing the new economic system requires also change at the governance levels, notably the role of the state in limiting throughput and distributing wealth more equally, although this is not included as source material.
Open coding	One of the sources of this vision (Nesterova & Buch-Hansen) refers to the inner being of people as a crucial yet underexplored aspect for a degrowth transformation. A genuine concern about the self, others (humans and non-humans) and nature would need to become widely shared. We need to nurture the 'mode of being' instead of the 'mode of having'. The mode of being revolves around inherent human capacities such as joy, awe, self-transcendence and self-actualization (=self-realization).

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Economics of Biodiversity (16)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	To introduce natural capital along with human capital into economic models to better deal with biodiversity loss. It calls for a major economic shift to incorporate the economics of biodiversity and ecosystem services into economics.
The 'What'	The principles articulated by the vision are useful to describe the 'What'. Humans are embedded in part of nature. The biosphere is bounded and so the global economy is bounded. The biosphere is a regenerative entity and its ecosystems are self-regulating. The economics of biodiversity advocated here is the economics of the entire biosphere. Nature nourishes and nurtures humans, and it is largely mobile. Market prices are imperfect - there is always a difference between prices paid for nature's goods and services and their social values (externality). Disclosure is thus necessary. Since many natural processes are silent and invisible it is not always possible to trace harms on nature to responsible parties, so no clear enforcement mechanism for socially responsible conduct exists. However, there is the possibility of self-monitoring which requires having an affection for nature and natural processes. A common future requires all of us to be naturalists.
Broad Values	Human embeddedness in nature. Human ingenuity for the common good. Affection for nature. Ecosystems as common pool resources. Economics of the biosphere. Participatory democracy and cooperation. Inclusive wealth (encompassing produced, human, and natural capital). Social wellbeing. Equity. Beyond materialism.
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	Although nature nourishes and nurtures humans, it is more than an economic good and it therefore has <u>intrinsic value</u> . Affection for nature should be developed if self-monitoring of conduct vis-a-vis nature is to work -> this also speaks of intrinsic value but can also be <u>relational value</u> . Notions of human embeddedness in nature also relate to relational value. <u>Instrumental value</u> is also present as nature is considered as natural capital in economic models which can be expressed in monetary value. Nature is thus valued for its services including provisioning (e.g., food), cultural and regulating (e.g., systemic resilience). However, the intrinsic and relational components present in the vision and the precautions taken by the authors (recognition of imperfect market prices) suggest that the instrumental orientation is moderate.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Land-use change</u> : It refers to it when it recognizes that modern agriculture (monocultures) produces a lot of food at the cost of biodiversity. It says that food production (meat) and agricultural practices need fundamental restructuring. The summary does not mention other direct drivers.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Economic</u> : The impacts on the biosphere increase with affluence, but so does efficiency. We need to reduce per capita global consumption and ensure that demands do not exceed nature's supply. Although it recognizes that the egalitarian objectives of SDGs appear to clash with the global need to reduce the ecological footprint of humans. We need to increase the efficiency with which the biosphere's supply of goods

	<p>and services is converted into global output and returned to the biosphere as waste. Payments for ecosystem services can be based on the principle that beneficiaries should pay to preserve and restore them (this point is related to ILK). Need to adopt inclusive metrics of economic success towards sustainable paths (beyond GDP).</p> <p><u>Demographic</u>: Lower future global population from what it is today. Population growth needs to transition to replacement fertility rates.</p> <p><u>Technological</u>: The report makes clear that human economies are embedded in nature and questions the assumption that technological advances (engines of economic growth) will allow humans to break free of nature. However, it also calls for certain technological advances (I assume those allowing us to use nature more efficiently, but it does not explain what kind of advances).</p> <p><u>Governance</u>: Ecosystems can be considered common pool resources. Participatory democracy offers a mechanism by which knowledge can inform how resources are used (based on cooperation). Here, sanctions for breaking agreements are important.</p> <p><u>Actions</u>: Invest in nature through conservation and restoration to increase our stock of nature and its regenerative rate.</p> <p><u>Structures</u>: Transform institutions and systems to enable changes for future generations.</p>
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries (ID=1, 21, 27, 54, 30, 31, 36, 59, 66, 71, 72, 74)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	To build an economic system that is within the 'safe and just operating space' meaning that humans can live well while keeping the impacts of their activities within planetary boundaries. While it counters conventional economics it is also designed to be appealing to a broad spectrum of stakeholders beyond radical social movements.
The 'What'	The economy delivers good human mental and physical health, greater equality and fairness, good social relationships in a flourishing natural environment. The economy gives value to activities driven by collaboration and sharing, recycling, and upcycling. The boundaries between producers and consumers are blurred. Ecosystems regenerate, the global commons are extended, communities are safe and healthy, wealth is more equitably and fairly distributed. The economy uses renewables and develops purpose-driven business with social and environmental aims. It also creates metrics that reflect real value. These activities enable humans to live well within planetary boundaries, achieving environmental sustainability, an equitable distribution of wealth and opportunity within and between generations, and an efficient allocation of resources to provide high levels of human wellbeing. Current emphasis on resource efficiency is complemented by the recognition of the need to reduce the overall amount of materials and energy used by the economy. In the Doughnut Economics (one of the sources of this vision) planetary boundaries are an ecological ceiling beyond which there is an overshoot of Earth's life-support systems, including climate change, ocean acidification, and biodiversity loss among other geophysical boundaries. The inner boundary presents a social foundation below which there are shortfalls in human wellbeing, with twelve dimensions drawn from internationally agreed minimum standards, including water, food, health, education, income and work, peace and justice, political voice, social equity, gender equality, housing, networks, and energy. The space in between these boundaries is an ecologically safe and socially just space in which all of humanity has the chance to thrive. Governance systems are aimed at fair, responsible, just and accountable governance that recognizes the interconnectedness between environment, society and economy in a way that is compatible with the SDGs.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature. Sufficiency. Equality and fairness. Participation. Sustainable and holistic wellbeing, quality of life. Stewardship of the whole system. Co-creation of collective value. Cosmopolitan localism. Democracy. Ecological regenerativity. Reciprocity. Circularity. Relationality. Connectedness (or connection). Dignity.

<p>Specific Values of Nature <u>Instrumental values</u> <u>Intrinsic values</u> <u>Relational values</u></p>	<p>Resource sanctuaries and limits to large infrastructures speak to the intrinsic value of nature. Stewardship, localism and relationality speak to relational value of nature. The instrumental component is also present as nature is valued for its contributions to wellbeing (e.g., when calculating the resource intensity of certain ecosystem service).</p>
<p>Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Reducing the overall consumption of materials and energy and situating the economy within planetary boundaries de facto affects all of these drivers. Similarly, the transformative policies identified in SSP0 (resource caps, resource sanctuaries, limits to large infrastructures, redistributive green taxation, work reduction schemes, agroecological development, compact urban planning and restrictions to advertising) would have a range of effects over all the direct drivers.</p>
<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Economic</i>: the vision aspires to create an economic system that delivers high levels of wellbeing for all within planetary boundaries. It thus fundamentally counters current economic drivers (see 'What') by moving away from the growth imperative and freeing biodiversity policies from it, i.e. biodiversity policies are not constrained to only those compatible with GDP growth. ● <i>Governance</i>: these economic changes go hand in hand with changes in governance (see 'What'). Plus the international community adopts a set of sustainable wellbeing indicators in substitution of GDP. ● <i>Demographic</i>: in some sources of the vision the population is expected to decline and stabilize at a sustainable level. ● <i>Technology</i>: in the new system, the main orientation of technology is not to fuel production and consumption but to liberate time for introspection and learning.
<p>Open coding</p>	<p>Connection, connectedness or collective awareness of the human embeddedness in the Earth's life network are notions present in some of the sources used to characterize this vision.</p>

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Natural Social Contract (ID=69)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly, but information is lacking for Specific values and Direct drivers.
Main Purpose or Goal	To describe a new social contract (coined as a Natural Social Contract) that is able to overcome the societal, environmental and economic problems we face today, as well as some of the pathways leading us there.
The 'What'	A society that is more humane and fairer and above all less destructive to people and nature. A Natural Social Contract that does justice to a human being's natural state (group life) and to the natural position of humankind and society within a larger ecosystem (the planet Earth). Society is regarded as a social-ecological system where people are members of a community and part of a natural ecosystem. This system is sustainable over the long term and there is general welfare. The approach is holistic. It is based on co-evolutionary principles accounting for evolutionary processes plus the notion of interconnectedness.
Broad Values	Fairness and equality. Long-term sustainability. General welfare. Responsibility. One of the key 'carriers of change' as they call it, is the creation of a new imaginary (Natural Social Contract and Wellbeing Economy) based in an ontology of interconnectedness and elimination of irresponsibility.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	The relational approach based on social-ecological systems and interconnectedness can be related to relational values. But more information is needed on specific values.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Not mentioned.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Economic</u> . The new society emerging from the Natural Social Contract recalibrates and puts an end to unlimited economic growth, overconsumption, and over-individualization, for the benefit of ourselves, our planet and future generations. It speaks about hybrid sphere (business having multiple goals) and alternative economy. Suggests going beyond GDP. It is important to note that this vision incorporates Doughnut economics, Wellbeing economics, and Economy for the common good. <u>Governance</u> : It speaks about co-evolutionary governance by actor coalitions. Coalitions are mentioned between alternative economy actors and regime actors to find common ground, including business models with multiple value creation aspirations. Practices of so-called 'evolutionary governance' are also important to synchronize agendas between different actors. In addition, three models of governance are mentioned: collaborative governance (deliberative, consensus-seeking, oriented to joint production of results/solutions, with social innovation and shared values and goals); evolutionary steering (nurturing variation, fostering coordination and adaptation of selection environment, via innovation and environmental policies, creating path dependencies in desirable ways through strategic niche management); and adaptive governance (coalition of the willing, mobilize actor networks, and support research/innovation). Values underlying institutional design:

	<p>Adaptive, reflexive, deliberative governance approaches; equal/fair (re-)distribution of risks, costs, benefits; arrangements for collective decision-making; reflexive monitoring; conflict prevention and resolution mechanisms; embedded activities/polycentric governance; policy learning.</p> <p><u>Actions:</u> It includes missions for making society more fair, more equal, and more sustainable (the synthesis does not describe these missions). There are links to the SDGs. It mentions the danger that such policies run counter to each other or are perceived in such a way. It argues for systemic leverage points for transformation. Locally rooted and internationally networked socio-ecological movements are mentioned as key actors (decisions to be taken at the most local level possible while being internationally connected).</p>
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Ecocivilization (352)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes. Source (website) easily findable and readable (English).
Main Purpose or Goal	To envisage a new civilization that focuses directly on Earth's biodiversity.
The 'What'	The new civilization is directly focused on Earth's biodiversity. ILK and alternative knowledge holders actively contribute to this new civilization, but it also speaks to a very broad range of sectors and participants. The world is balanced, just and connected. Beings have a clear purpose and are actively inter-related, they live in a land which is rich in resources, societies have deep networks of cooperation, the awareness is constantly evolving towards higher levels, relationships are kept alive. Humanity serves the Earth in connected, supportive collaboration for collective wellbeing. Humans have reached the deep understanding that they are part of a common space that we share with a common consciousness. The essence of society is relationships. The principle of competition is no longer regulating social logic, but rather that of endless collaboration.
Broad Values	A more just world. A more balanced world. Constantly evolving levels of awareness. The movement encourages thinking about the way humans live and co-exist with nature.
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	The direct focus of the new civilization envisaged by this social movement is the Earth's biodiversity. We can assume a strong intrinsic orientation. An orientation towards relational values emerges from the following: recognition of ILK, encouragement of thinking about the way humans co-exist with nature, and the strong emphasis on relationships. The instrumental component does not seem to play out.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Natural resource use and exploitation</u> : one of the five entities of Ecocivilization is Land which is envisioned to be rich in resources. Otherwise in the synthesis there is no other reference to direct drivers.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Governance</u> : Society is another of the five entities of Ecocivilization. It is envisioned as having deep networks of cooperation. <u>Power</u> : The movement is women-led (this is referred to as a dream). <u>Actions</u> : Each year the movement has a different focus to evoke transformative change in thinking and action towards a better world (e.g., this year is about water). Structures: are based on systems and in the form of networks that nurture a society whose essence is relationships.
Open coding	Emphasis on interconnected beings, higher awareness and understanding that humans share the space with a common consciousness -> all this speaks directly to spiritual visions.

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Water, forest and agriculture visions for future Ukraine (ID=232, 1047, 1048)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision's main purpose seems to be to provide an inspirational endpoint for the transformations in water, forest and agricultural sectors of Ukraine.
The 'What'	In 2100, Ukraine is prosperous, nature-friendly, carbon-neutral, and resistant to climate change, where natural resources are used in a balanced way, preserved and restored. Aquatic ecosystems and related biodiversity are preserved, restored, and managed through integrated basin management principle, the use of financial instruments and nature-based solutions to achieve a good environmental state of waters and optimize water use. By 2030-2060, integrated landscape management in the forest, water and agricultural sectors is achieved by applying the best practices of close-to-nature silviculture and enhanced reproduction of forests, including agroforestry. There is a new economic model based on ecosystem services. Decisions in the forest sector are made with the priority of biodiversity conservation, and with the help of a transparent monitoring system. By 2030-2060 the agricultural landscape of Ukraine is close to nature - with balanced proportions of agricultural land, forests, forest strips, steppes and other natural or anthropogenic elements. Such a balance is achieved using nature-based solutions, ecologically conscious consumption and effective cooperation of the state, communities and businesses, science and education. The agri-food sector is generally climate-neutral.
Broad Values	As part of the general and sector-specific visions, we have the following broad values: prosperity, nature-friendliness, balanced use of natural resources, biodiversity conservation and restoration, cooperation.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	The visions are rather economic and focused on resources, therefore speaking mostly to the instrumental value of nature. However, the vision on forests prioritizes biodiversity conservation therefore an intrinsic value component could be deduced. The vision for the agricultural sector describes a balance between different land-covers including anthropogenic elements, pointing to a cultural landscape and thus a relational value component. Coder says "The motivation of the environmental component of the general vision is weaker than the economic component" we can thus assume a stronger instrumental orientation.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Direct drivers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Climate change</i> is referred to when envisioning a carbon-neutral future. ● <i>Natural resource use and exploitation</i> can be considered to be implicit there when expressing the wish to use natural resources in a balanced way. ● <i>Land-use change</i> is considered when defending close-to-nature silviculture, agroforestry and a balance between land-uses in the agricultural landscape. ● <i>Sea use</i> could be considered to be there when expressing the vision of preserving aquatic ecosystems and related biodiversity although it focuses mostly on freshwater ecosystems. Actions: Nature-based solutions.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Economic</i>: A new economic model based on ecosystem services supports an integrated landscape management across forest, water and agriculture sectors. Ecologically conscious consumption contributes to

<p><i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>achieve a balance between land-uses in the agricultural landscape. Business are one of the actors cooperating to reach this balance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Governance:</i> Effective cooperation of the state, communities, businesses, science and education contributes to achieve a balance between land-uses in the agricultural landscape. Vision aspires to influence national governance in efforts to harmonize the development with the EU.
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Steps for Change (ID=85)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Not enough information in the description. Going to the source is needed and possible (video). It is a very beautiful and touching dance piece that motivates and inspires, but it is difficult to extract a vision (the 'What') and fill the other categories. This is due to the format of the source, i.e., an artistic expression without words. We filled the categories based on a subjective interpretation of the images, colours, etc.
Main Purpose or Goal	The dance piece was commissioned for the 7th IPBES Plenary at the occasion of the approval of the Global Biodiversity Assessment (2019). It aims to create awareness of the planet's plight of biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation, highlighting the urgent need for "a step change".
The 'What'	It starts with children stating that we are nature and that we need a step change, suggesting that innocence is the root of change to conserve nature. The dance which is entirely performed by young girls (aged 7-13), starts with a group of marine organisms affected by plastic pollution. Marine blue dominates. The group of organisms seems to struggle to get out of the sea. Calmness is now back. Dancers are a coral reef moving in unison. Backdrops show beautiful and colorful images of coral reefs. Suddenly coral reefs turn white: bleaching. It is now the turn of backdrops with phosphorescent jellyfish. Obviously now the marine organism is heavily threatened as the dancers perform a dark sequence overseen by the eye of a sort of reptile. We are now in the land. Dancers look exhausted. The backdrop earth is undergoing a severe drought. However, the dance's energy picks up, but not for long time. Dancers are exhausted again. Finally, rain drops start fertilizing the land and the first plants after extreme drought germinate. A lush, humid forest emerges with generous water flowing down. Violin music suggests rebirth. The dancers are now also in the backdrops video inside the forest together with a rich fauna and flora. Finally, a thriving biodiversity is restored. The children that appeared at the beginning are also in the backdrops, inside the forest. The piece ends here amidst the applause. Dancers descend from stage towards the audience amidst a standing ovation by the IPBES plenary. Thus, the dance and backdrops scenery move from disastrous trajectory (environmental degradation) to desired future (thriving biodiversity). The human dependency with nature is highlighted.
Broad Values	It seeks to inspire and encourage feelings, deep thinking, and responses by humans to biodiversity loss.
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	Not possible to know given the absence of words, but I would guess somewhere between intrinsic (beauty of nature which has a value in itself) and relational (given human dependence and evocative relationship through dance). The instrumental aspect does not seem to be present.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Climate change</u> : The piece uses examples of corals (bleaching) and droughts & rising temperatures to inspire action. Therefore we can say it speaks about climate change. <u>Pollution</u> : Reference to plastic pollution (see the 'What'). <u>Invasive species</u> : The video's description says that one of the sequences is about invasive species (probably the one with the reptile's eye).
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and</i>	<u>Actions</u> : restoration of nature (last sequence).

<i>governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Latin American Agroecological Society (SOCLA) (ID=830)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly yes but we went to the website and looked for information that was lacking for specific values of nature, direct drivers, and indirect drivers. This information was retrieved from several documents included in the website. However, it was not possible to read them all (there are dozens of publications).
Main Purpose or Goal	Implicit vision of the Latin American Agroecological Society. This organization promotes agroecology to achieve rural development and sustainable food systems in Latin America.
The 'What'	The vision is about promoting agroecology from different forms of knowledge and through the dialogue of knowledge as a strategy to achieve the sustainability of peoples and food systems in Latin America, emphasizing the values of Good Living / Living Well; food sovereignty; the restoration, health and integrity of ecosystems and socio-ecological systems; the protection, conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity; the reevaluation of biocultural heritage and traditional knowledge; and strengthening of integral well-being. The vision includes many countries such as Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Colombia, El Salvador, among others.
Broad Values	Good Living. Food sovereignty. Ecosystems' health and integrity. Biodiversity conservation and sustainable use. Reevaluation of biocultural heritage and traditional knowledge. Integral wellbeing.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Agroecology can be assumed to speak to a relational approach to nature. Reference (in the website) to responding to needs from farmers and indigenous peoples reinforces this assumption.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Climate change</u> : It is mentioned as one of the topics about which they disseminate knowledge (social-ecological resilience to climate change, see below). Also, addressing climate change adaptation challenges is an area of joint work with FAO. <u>Land-use change</u> : We can assume that the vision targets land-use change through its emphasis on agroecology and food systems. <u>Natural resource use and exploitation</u> : Together with FAO, they aspire to work for species diversification, efficiency in resource use, to conserve and improve natural resources and biodiversity. <u>Pollution</u> : Promote alternative to agrochemicals and transgenics.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Technology</u> : Among the objectives, they promote the development of technologies and techniques based on agroecology principles. <u>Governance</u> : Among their objectives, there is to strengthen regional and international cooperation to achieve the rest of objectives. Promote responsible governance mechanisms efficient at different scales for sustainable agriculture diet. <u>Economic</u> : Promote circular and solidary economies connecting producers and consumers as a social base for an inclusive and sustainable development. <u>Actions</u> : (The goals of the association hence the activities they are meant to conduct are taken as actions towards the vision). Their goals are to promote, coordinate and facilitate research, teaching and the diffusion of multiple aspects related to agroecology for sustainability, food sovereignty and socio-ecological resilience to climate change. They seek to respond to the needs and demands of farmers, peasants, and indigenous organizations. The promotion of agroecology is a strategy for social transformation. This includes rural extension and capacity-building. Some of these actions are promoted regionally. Their approach is of action-research. <u>Structures</u> : Considered by coder to target the intent of the system since they propose a paradigm change in the food systems, trade and human

	health. Together with FAO they want to work on legal frameworks, policies and practices that promote agroecology. <u>Power shifts</u> : Focus on (gender) equity.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (ID=834)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly yes, but information on specific values of nature was lacking. Going through all the website materials was considered unfeasible. Instead, this category was filled by looking at those SDG highlighted by FAO as being relevant for their work.
Main Purpose or Goal	This is the vision of the FAO, agency that leads the international effort to end hunger. Its goal is to achieve food security for all and enhancing people's quality of life through nutrition.
The 'What'	A world where hunger does not exist. There is food security for all. Everybody has regular access to sufficient and good-quality food. The vision has a global scope and includes both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, with a focus on sustainable use and management.
Broad Values	Food security. Inclusive and sustainable agricultural systems. Eradication of hunger and malnutrition. Resilient and equitable food systems.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	References to food systems, agricultural productivity, food security sit between an instrumental and a relational value orientation. The information and illustrations used to report on those SDG relevant to FAO's work portray rural communities living in, working in and eating from their agricultural landscapes. This speaks to a relational approach. Nature is however also valued for what it brings to humans: food, water and energy, hence also the instrumental approach is present. Those SDG related to conservation of marine and terrestrial life have some components of intrinsic values, perhaps of less importance than relational and instrumental.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Information on direct drivers was lacking but was extracted from FAO's links to SDG as reported by coder: <u>Climate change</u> : They say that food systems must overcome their dependence on fossil fuels. In addition, agriculture is considered critical to respond to climate change. <u>Natural resource use and exploitation</u> : some of their activities speak to this, like the protection of bees and the fight against excessive fishing (see below). <u>Land-use change</u> : since it is about food systems and there is the mention to sustainable agricultural mechanization and promotion of sustainable agricultural practices, which implies a change in land-use intensity, it can be considered part of land-use change. The mention of rural investment to counteract unmanageable urbanization also speaks about land-use change.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<u>Governance</u> : inclusive partnerships contribute to achieve their vision of eradicating hunger and ensuring sustainable food systems for all. <u>Actions</u> : (Current initiatives of FAO are taken as actions). Nowadays their initiatives are sustainable agricultural mechanization, corporate environmental responsibility, promoting environmental and social standards, among others. They also organize events to raise awareness about nutrition, protect species such as bees, fight against illegal/unreported/unregulated fishing, among others. In 2020 (Year of Plant Health) they raised awareness about reducing the spread of pests and plant diseases which can harm food security, the environment, and economies. Links to all SDGs mentioned (from SDG 1 to SDG 17) since they all have a connection with food systems. <u>Structures and power shifts</u> : end poverty in rural areas and low-income economies, gender equality, innovation opens new markets for small farmers, land reform can offer fairer access to rural land. FAO advocates for policies and actions prioritizing smallholder farmers, sustainable agricultural practices, climate change adaptation, and biodiversity conservation to achieve their vision of eradicating hunger.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Agricultural and Rural Prospective Initiative (IPAR) (ID=879)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly yes, but information on direct drivers was scarce and information on specific values of nature was lacking. However, going through all their website materials to get this information is considered unfeasible.
Main Purpose or Goal	This is the vision of IPAR, a space for reflection, dialogue, and proposals for concerted agricultural and rural policies in Senegal and in the West African region. This initiative was promoted by specialists in agriculture and the rural world who supported peasant organizations and were interested in creating permanent spaces for strategic and prospective reflection.
The 'What'	To be an institution of strategic and prospective analysis capable of influencing, at the national and subregional level, public policies in the agricultural and rural sector, as well as in the processes of economic and social transformation.
Broad Values	Sustainable Development Goals (articles about SDG are published in their webpage). SDG 3 (Good health and well-being) is particularly important (especially in relation to food production). Sustainable use of ecosystems. Global sustainability. Quality of life.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Biodiversity is not clearly stated.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<i>Climate change:</i> In their webpage they publish articles about climate change, how to adapt or mitigate it, its impacts on agriculture. <i>Land-use change:</i> To the extent that they deal with agriculture and sustainability, although not explicitly stated.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<i>Economic:</i> They created a common market within the subregion. They promote the liberalization of the economies. <i>Governance:</i> In their website they publish articles about governance of natural resources and land such as watershed management. <i>Actions:</i> (Current mission and purpose of IPAR are taken as actions). Its mission and purpose revolve around three main axes: research, capacity development and the organization of exchange and debate forums. IPAR's role is to co-produce analyses, offer policy options and strategies, influence national government, and develop subregional and international public policies. The founders of IPAR have given themselves the task of supporting/helping public and private actors at all levels (local, regional and national), providing them with information, analysis, and research work necessary for their strategic reflections and with a vision of the future. They carry out programs to monitor the development of SDG 3 (Good health and well-being for all) to make sure that no one is left out. <i>Structures:</i> (IPAR's intent for the long term is taken as intended change in structures). In the long term, they plan to participate in the creation of sustainable institutional capacities in the field of agricultural and rural forecasting and to promote and support alternative paths to the policies and programs underway in Senegal and West Africa. They participate in the elaboration of public policies related to agrarian reform. They target the social structures and institutions. <i>Power shifts:</i> In their webpage they publish articles on women's access to land and artisanal fishing.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
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Vision Id and Name (if available)	Agroecological Resources Space (L'era) (ID=887)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly yes, but information on specific values of nature was lacking. Their website was checked for this.
Main Purpose or Goal	L'era is an association made up of peasant women and men, small gardeners, technicians, neo-rurals, students and people interested in the peasantry. Its purpose is to advance towards greater social recognition of an agricultural sector that contributes to food sovereignty and fair relations between consumption and production.
The 'What'	An agricultural sector that gains greater recognition by society, that contributes to the food sovereignty of its territory, and that has fair trade relations between the sphere of consumption and production and between countries. They believe in a peasantry that works according to a holistic concept, integrating the environment and people's rights, to move towards a truly agroecological agriculture. L'era envisions a society that respects and cares for the Earth, fostering agroecological practices that prioritize the health of ecosystems and communities. They aim to create a world where agricultural systems are based on agroecology, promoting sustainable and resilient food production that nurtures biodiversity, cultural heritage, and social justice. L'era seeks to develop agroecological models that promote autonomy, local economies, and food sovereignty, while addressing the environmental, social, and economic challenges of our time. Their vision emphasizes the importance of agroecology as a transformative approach to agriculture that integrates ecological principles, local knowledge, and social equity. They envision a shift towards agroecological practices that protect and restore ecosystems, promote resilient and diversified farming systems, and ensure the well-being and empowerment of farmers and communities.
Broad Values	Agroecology. Autonomy. Local economies. Peasantry. Food sovereignty. Social justice. Cultural heritage. Diversified farming systems. They promote a change in worldviews.
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	Their approach aligns mostly with the relational value component (cultural heritage, local varieties, agroecology, etc.). Perhaps some elements of intrinsic values are there too, for example in one of the objectives they state that they are one organism among many in this planet and that they wish to balance their role in the complexity of ecological systems. We assume they assign intrinsic value to this ecological system. Also, in some of the approaches they promote (like the living soil agriculture) they get inspiration and try to mimic nature in its soil-forming and biodiversity producing functions). Similarly, an intrinsic value can be derived but in any case, is of less importance than the relational one.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<i>Land-use change:</i> transition to agroecology implies changes in the way land is used. <i>Climate change:</i> they promote an agriculture that helps mitigate climate change and stops being one of the main sources of greenhouse gases.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<i>Economic:</i> Focus on autonomy and the development of local economies. <i>Technological:</i> They provide technical advice related to agroecology. They have projects on ecological production practices and techniques, renewable energy and bioconstruction. <i>Actions / power shifts:</i> They envision a shift towards agroecological practices that protect and restore ecosystems, promote resilient and diversified farming systems and ensure the wellbeing and empowerment of farmers and communities. (Activities of the association are taken as

	actions as well). They publish informative material on any medium, provide assistance and technical advice services, promote training in ecological production and energy sustainability, and education in critical and ecological consumption. They have projects about ecological production practices and techniques, renewable energy, bioconstruction, and self-sufficiency. They preserve and disseminate the local varieties that are typical of their territory.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	World Farmers Organization (WFO) (ID=893)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly yes, but information on specific values of nature was lacking. Their website was checked for this but there are too many materials – going through all of them is considered unfeasible.
Main Purpose or Goal	The WFO brings together national farmer organizations and agricultural cooperatives from around the world. Its mission is to represent the voice of farmers and advocate on their behalf in all international processes that affect them, including those related to agriculture, nutrition and sustainability.
The 'What'	A world where the voice of the farmers is heard, where policies and programs have been put in place to improve the livelihoods of rural communities, and where agriculture contributes to address humanity's pressing challenges. The so-called 'farmer-driven approach' to address these challenges has been strengthened. This means that the path that the world's farmers are currently building and following to achieve a more sustainable future for all humanity reaches has reached its full potential. Farmers include women, men and youth who deal with small, medium and large farms and cooperatives.
Broad Values	Social role of agriculture. Sustainable agriculture. Rural livelihoods. Sustainable use of ecosystems. Environmental sustainability.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<i>Climate change:</i> The vision mentions best practices that farmers are already implementing as practical solutions to climate change mitigation and adaptation. These practices are the basis of their 'Farmer Driven Climate Change Agenda' adopted by WFO to enhance the position of farmers in global discussions on climate change. Among the different international processes where they participate, there is the COP of the Climate Change Convention. <i>Land-use change:</i> As the vision deals with sustainable agriculture.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	<i>Technology:</i> One of their projects seeks to empower farmers through technology. They consider that innovation and digitalization in the agricultural sector are crucial to help farmers face global challenges. In the mentioned project, agricultural technology experts, farmers and farmer organizations work together to digitally transform the agri-food sector with global scalability and replicability potential. In general, they encourage the adoption of new technologies. <i>Actions:</i> 1) Capacity-building programs aimed at training young farmers as future leaders in the agricultural sectors. 2) Enhance the position and leadership of the farmers in the global political discussion on climate change and agriculture (see climate change in 'Direct drivers'). This is intended to be a farmers-driven, science-based and results oriented process. 3) The project 'Transitional Agriculture' promotes exchange between farmers' organizations from several countries on agricultural issues relevant to development policy. 4) Involvement in negotiations to represent the voice of farmers. For example, thanks to their involvement in negotiations for SDG, they claim that an entire goal (SDG 2) is dedicated to food security and agriculture. 5) Capacity-building initiatives for farmers. <i>Actions/structures:</i> The objective of WFO is to create the conditions for the adoption of policies and programs that can improve the

	<p>economic environment and the livelihoods of producers and of rural communities, strengthening the contribution of agriculture to address humanity's challenges.</p> <p><u>Power shifts</u>: They strive to empower farmers to become agents of change and to drive the transformation of agricultural systems towards more sustainable and resilient models (see initiatives to encourage leadership and participation of farmers, especially point 2 and 4 under actions).</p>
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	The Ministry for the Future (ID=162)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No. It was necessary to consult other sources to gather basic information (e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Ministry_for_the_Future)
Main Purpose or Goal	To act as an advocate for the world's future generations of citizens as if their rights were as valid as the present generation.
The 'What'	A new international climate-crisis body has been “charged with defending all living creatures present and future who cannot speak for themselves” and is quickly dubbed the Ministry for the Future. The book narrates through fictional testimonies how climate change will affect us all. The vision is not of a desolate, apocalyptic world, but of a future that is already upon us. The vision clearly focuses on what to do to accelerate the walk toward Paris Agreement’s goals.
Broad Values	Integration human nature Responsibility Rights for nature Inclusiveness Intergenerational equity
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: fully embrace the importance of biodiversity and its threats for current and future generations. A coordinated global round of unconventional quantitative easing through the issuance of a complementary currency, called the carbon coin, to be issued in proportion to the mass of carbon that is mitigated. The monetary concept, called carbon quantitative easing, is based on a specific real-life policy proposal, called a Global Carbon Reward, and an academic paper referred to throughout the book as the "Chen Paper".
Direct Drivers	Climate change Land degradation Pollution Natural resource use and exploitation
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	Economics: a coordinated global round of unconventional quantitative easing through the issuance of a complementary currency, called the carbon coin, to be issued in proportion to the mass of carbon that is mitigated. Technology: technological innovations are mentioned but less elaborated. Governance: the vision is focused on the role of a head of a UN-hosted institution.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Princess Mononoke (ID=166)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes
Main Purpose or Goal	To portray a thought-provoking and visually stunning narrative on the importance of preserving nature and coexisting with the world around us.
The 'What'	The film depicts a clash between human civilization and the natural world, where humans exploit resources and destroy the environment to build their cities and wage wars. The movie also highlights the consequences of this behavior, as the spirits of the forest fight back, resulting in a battle for the survival of both sides. It is about the balance between how humans try to answer their needs and how ecosystems can thrive.
Broad Values	Harmony with human nature Equity Justice Responsibility Stewardship of the whole system Gender and inclusiveness
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: the film refers to the wild environment of the natural world and its fierce resistance to human interference, while humans represent the force of industrialization and civilization, which seeks to conquer and dominate the natural world. Suggesting to the viewer that the preservation of nature is necessary to maintain a peaceful functioning society, and if one abuses the other, destruction will ensue.
Direct Drivers	Land degradation Natural resource use and exploitation
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	Economics: The story addresses the economic values (ie., greed) deeply engrained in the western system.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Radical ruralities in practice: Negotiating buen vivir in a Colombian network of sustainability (ID=588)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes
Main Purpose or Goal	To show a departure from the modern development narrative through a turn towards a more biocentric, relational and collective means of understanding and being in the world.
The 'What'	It illustrates the continual process of negotiation and sacrifice, where visions – and hence expectations – are continually being adjusted to the realities on the ground, implying a willingness to change ingrained habits of living. Put forward as an alternative to modern development, buen vivir resonates for many, yet putting them into practice highlights the contradictions and challenges of transitioning to new ways of living and being. Buen vivir is a concept in construction. It has the potential to articulate diverse societal groups such as indigenous and non-indigenous groups around shared values of buen vivir, contributing to reflections on novel ways of building peaceful relations between people and nature.
Broad Values	Harmony with human nature Fairness Justice Interdependent rights between nature and people Inclusiveness Responsibility Indigenous cosmovisions Solidarity Traditions and customs
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: Buen vivir represents a departure from the modern development narrative through a turn towards a more biocentric, relational and collective means of understanding and being in the world. Most important is relations to self, then to family as an empowering source of change, while maintaining loving and trusting relations with neighbors and between community members.
Direct Drivers	Land use Natural and resource use and exploitation
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	Economic: radical ruralities diverge from the inherently capitalistic logic of the other narratives by striving for the production of truly different forms of rural space, which not just extend the scope of rural possibilities but also concern the issues of the ideological underpinnings of the forms of rural space. Governance: The concept of ‘territory’ (and its rights) plays an important role within buen vivir, integrating the natural and spiritual diversity of all forms of life through customs, traditions, languages, worldviews, principles and values.
Open coding	A territory is understood as a living dynamic system made up of biotic networks ranging from the cellular world to the ayllu – the Aymaran word for cosmos. In this sense, Buen vivir prioritizes the interdependent rights

	of the cosmos and humans, relating to the land as a 'Mother that one would not hurt' instead of as an objective commodity. The notion of the planet as a Mother related to several spiritual visions (Mother Earth, Tao).
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	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Sense of place and experimentation in urban sustainability transitions: the Resilience Lab in Carnisse, Rotterdam, The Netherlands (ID=739)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	To creating new sense of urban place by establishing new meanings of place, and the strengthening of relations between people and their neighborhood as well as the creation of new relations within and across the community
The 'What'	<p>Urban living labs can connect a sense of change with a sense of place by co-creating new narratives of place, by co-producing knowledge on new practices and new relations between people and place, and by allowing the co-design or (re)establishment of places with symbolic meaning. As such, urban living labs facilitate urban sustainability transitions.</p> <p>The Resilience Lab did not seek to shift a certain regime on the neighborhood level, but tried to stimulate certain boundary conditions (awareness, skills, capabilities, social cohesion, etc.) as to address several regime shifts in practice within systems</p>
Broad Values	<p>Harmony with human nature</p> <p>A more open and friendly space</p> <p>Responsibility</p> <p>General welfare</p> <p>Health care</p> <p>Sense of place</p> <p>Solidarity</p> <p>Social cohesion</p>
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: it creates a new sense of place by establishing new meanings of place, and the strengthening of relations between people and their neighborhood as well as the creation of new relations within and across the community.
Direct Drivers	<p>Land use</p> <p>Natural resource and exploitation</p>
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<p>Values: urban places have been reclaimed as a sort of counter movement by the local communities and transformed into more inclusive, open and broadly supported places.</p> <p>Governance: The vision combined with the symbolic places and alternative practices, created a narrative of place which in turn, contributed to creating a place identity and increased the sense of community. As such, creating sense of place increased community agency that was empowered and self-directed to act to achieve the vision. Different engagement and participatory methodologies for establishing new forms of collaborations between citizens and the city, and new social relations between the residents.</p>
Open coding	
	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)

Vision Id and Name (if available)	Rhiz(h)ome (ID=741)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No, it was necessary to read the paper Hamann et al 2020: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2020.102526
Main Purpose or Goal	To develop a vision in which the emphasis is on highly decentralized governance and business, epitomized by a myriad of interconnected, small, and green cities across southern Africa. An empowered citizenry places value on fairness, knowledge-sharing, learning, self-fulfillment and environmental stewardship.
The 'What'	<p>There has been a fundamental shift in the nature and meaning of work. The alienating notion of labor has been replaced by an emphasis on societal contribution and opportunities for self-fulfillment, expression and agency. The economy has become process and service-based, rather than output-based. Society has ended its obsession with material goods. Businesses now specialize in creating opportunities for human fulfilment and the generation and sharing of knowledge.</p> <p>It is similar to the New Sustainability Paradigm group of scenarios, which envision a more globalized, cosmopolitan, culturally cross-fertilized, and economically connected society than the Eco-Communalism storylines.</p>
Broad Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Harmony with human nature Fairness Knowledge-sharing Learning Participation Justice Self-fulfillment Agency Environmental stewardship
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: The Earth is seen as a collective resource and base for prosperity, and land ownership has been fundamentally reimagined as stewardship. Nature is more of a source of inspiration and fundamental to the design of how cities and communities work
Direct Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land use Natural resource and exploitation

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: Reducing separation between races, genders, languages and cultures. Difference is valued and respected, and there is formal recourse for marginalized groups. Access to key resources, especially food, healthcare, housing, water, and energy is equitable and context-sensitive.</p> <p>Governance: Citizen-led governance by active, knowledgeable citizens that take responsibility; strong family structures and values; inclusion of deviance – not excluding people. The shift in governance structures and the economy was facilitated by technological developments, especially blockchain technology that enables decentralized, self-managed, and communally held records of ownership and exchange. This has enabled many previously voluntary activities and participation in citizen and governance structures to be appropriately rewarded.</p> <p>Technology: Technology has enabled high levels of direct participation in decision-making at multiple scales. This allows communities and economies to be local and deeply context-sensitive, and at the same time richly interconnected globally. Collaboration and partnership inform the underlying societal norms.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Radical TransLocal (ID=744)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No, it was necessary to read the paper Hamann et al 2020: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2020.102526
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision's main purpose seems to be to provide an inspirational return to community-driven decision-making based on indigenous knowledge and a deep connection to Mother Earth.
The 'What'	<p>It describes an eco-centric community-based movement that embraces social and environmental issues equally. Going back to the roots of humanity was a simple yet radical notion that captured the hearts of all across the globe.</p> <p>Consumption is guided by a machine learning system that accounts for the full ecological cost of every choice, and food production has been revolutionized by personal artificial meat processors.</p> <p>All decisions are bound by a deep commitment to the protection and health of the environment. There is an understanding that the Earth nurtures, heals, provides and supports.</p>
Broad Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptive learning Artful expression Indigenous cosmovision Community Responsibility Exchange of skills Intergenerational equity
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: it is a return to community-driven decision-making based on indigenous knowledge and a deep connection to Mother Earth. Society embraces learning and artful expression, and strives to exist in balance with nature.
Direct Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land use Natural resource and exploitation

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: Consumption is guided by a machine learning system that accounts for the full ecological cost of every choice, and food production has been revolutionized by personal artificial meat processors.</p> <p>Economics: The economy is a hybrid between sharing and gift economies, with different kinds of alternative currencies, supported by the VERITAS accounting system. There has been a reduction in economic migration, allowing people to move around between rural villages and cities because they choose to do so freely, not because of socio-economic hardship.</p> <p>Governance: it is a return to community-driven decision-making based on indigenous knowledge and a deep connection to Mother Earth. There are no nation states and communities are organized locally/regionally. A direct democracy allows for daily voting through electronic devices where citizens can cast votes on what needs to be done/decided. This system acknowledges stakeholder-based property rights, which increase community buy-in and investments in local assets and ecosystem services, as well as ethical modes of production and consumption.</p> <p>Technology: To assist individuals in making Earth-conscious decisions, VERITAS was developed. VERITAS – the Virtual Eco-centric Redistributive Index Tax Adaptive System – is an artificial intelligence that accounts for the full ecological cost of all the products that a person uses every day, and provides opportunities to improve one’s “eco-status”. Technology facilitated this movement by improving food production systems. Techno-food and the iMeat3000 (an artificial meat processor) changed the way the world interacted with nature in very much the same way that the smartphone of the 21st century changed the way humans communicated. This led to a decrease in industrial food production and waste, and also to an expansion of new kinds of designed health foods.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	<p>Deep connection to Mother Earth is the basis for community-driven decision-making. Links to spiritual visions and rest of inductive coding notes.</p>

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Twitter's vision on circular economy (ID=904)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No, it was necessary to read the paper in detail De Lima et al. (2022) https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S095965262203311X?via%3Dihub
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision's main purpose seems to be to assume economic, technological, and environmental transformation in order to use limited natural resources sustainably.
The 'What'	Twitter users argued that water management is crucial for avoiding the contamination of water supplies and reducing the risk of water scarcity. They tweeted that environmental compliance in the circular economy can be achieved via standards and certificates and extended producer responsibility schemes. It fosters restorative and regenerative systems that recover materials, components, and products (MCPs) in technical cycles and promote the self-renewal capacity of natural ecosystems.
Broad Values	Recircling Recovery Environmental sustainability Collaboration Resilience
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: The paper focuses on the analysis of Tweets around the concept of circular economy as it fosters the circularity of resources in production and consumption systems.
Direct Drivers	Land use change Natural resource and exploitation Climate change

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: the paper focuses on the concept of CE which has been framed as a pathway toward sustainable production and consumption systems. It fosters restorative and regenerative systems that recover materials, components, and products (MCPs) in technical cycles and promote the self-renewal capacity of natural ecosystems. Accordingly, the CE aims to tackle global sustainability challenges, including climate change, resource scarcity, and biodiversity loss.</p> <p>Economics: As a major part of the vision was collected from sectoral experts and business actors it might lack motivation for the general public, but be very motivating for businesses and governments.</p> <p>Governance: The results show that practitioners have mainstreamed the CE discourse, sharing reductionist views about the concept in terms of drivers, practices, and outcomes. Regarding environmental sustainability, the most frequently mentioned indicators were waste management. Environmental compliance was quoted in 5.53% tweets. Little attention was paid to supplier assessment. To achieve material efficiency, transparency and traceability were acknowledged as key strategies. Regarding managerial implications, this study provokes critical reflections on how the CE concept has been debated on Twitter, highlighting the need to identify the drivers, practices, and outcomes limiting and empowering the CE's vision and potential. practitioners largely dominated the CE discourse on Twitter, sharing oversimplified perspectives of the concept.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Ukraine Recovery Vision (ID=227, 229)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Not, it was necessary to read the full recovery plan https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/621f88db25fbf24758792dd8/62c166751fcf41105380a733_NRC%20Ukraine%27s%20Recovery%20Plan%20blueprint_ENG.pdf
Main Purpose or Goal	This general vision contains a strategic goal: “Re-build clean and safe environment and ensure sustainable development in line with the EU Green Deal.
The 'What'	This is a comprehensive programme of sustainable post-war restoration of Ukraine. Strategic components of the vision include climatic goals integrated in all the aspects of economy and societal life, minimised risks for environmental safety, reduction of industrial pollution, effective waste management, balanced use of natural resources, restoring and expanding of protected areas, biodiversity preservation, achieving the EU standards in environmental protection.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Sustainable and holistic wellbeing Democracy Resilience Quality of life Identity Prosperity Equity Justice Integration Recovery Social protection Health care Ability to tackle complex global challenges Sufficiency Autonomy Equality Integration/harmony humans-nature Ecology Inclusive wealth (encompassing produced, human, and natural capital)

<p>Specific Values of Nature</p>	<p>Instrumental: Boost business environment with aim to increase number of new businesses in Ukraine, Providing competitive access to funding is critical enabler for economic development, Transport infrastructure upgrade serves two goals – EU integration and interconnectedness within Ukraine boosts economy, Modernization of regions and housing, incl. large-scale energy efficiency program, is a strategic priority, Modernization of social infrastructure, Improve Education system with focus on key competences and innovation, Secure targeted and effective social policy, including returning refugees.</p> <p>Relational:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Re-build clean and safe environment -Construction of 10 European nature parks, -Construction of a network of ecoducs, -Construction of 10 centers for rehabilitation and rescue of wild animals <p>Increasing the area of protected areas up to 30%.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Creating an ecological web portal "Ecosystem" -Fixation and calculation of losses of war consequences -Ecological restoration of the territory of the Radical plant -Ecological restoration of Solotvino salt mines -Revitalization of the exclusion zone, reduction from 30 to 15 kilometers of zone -Construction of about 130 modern waste processing complexes -Ensuring the proper functioning of radioactive waste management facilities -Ukraine will support Europe's energy security and zero-carbon transition. -Preservation of natural ecosystems, WOW-nature: national parks for people -Creation of a network of regional centers for rehabilitation and rescue of wild animals in Ukraine -Creating a network of 15 ecoducs in Ukraine <p>Intrinsic: Restoration of wildlife in Ukraine</p>
<p>Direct Drivers</p>	<p>Pollution Natural resource and exploitation Climate change War</p>

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: Plan for gradual ramp-up of activities, with gradual increase of risk appetite, as unlikely to have “clean victory” and “clean peace”, or clear milestones to transition from “recovery” to “modernization”.</p> <p>Economics: This vision lies in the institutional development of Ukraine overall, the transformation of its economics by integrating into the EU, climate-resilient and low-carbon energy infrastructure, urban greening and revitalisation, digitalisation, etc. The vision aims to promote the effective banking system and financial markets. It aims for a proactive and efficient immigration policy, and to have a modernized and energy efficient housing and urban design. The recovery should enable Ukraine’s private investment and boost nation- wide entrepreneurship.</p> <p>Governance: The vision includes a robust participatory component – everyone may suggest a project to achieve the general vision. However, the overall process of stakeholders’ engagement is not straightforward enough. Implementation of a law-enforcement agencies reform (e.g., reducing punitive function of Security Service of Ukraine, strengthening independence of Economic Security Bureau of Ukraine). Development of architecture for climate governance (e.g. creation of coordinating agency ensuring sustainability strategy implementation across ministries, alignment of sustainability performance with budget, creation of accountability institutions)</p> <p>Specific tasks include creating a network of regional centres for rehabilitating and rescuing wild animals in Ukraine, creating a network of 15 ecoducs, constructing forest roads, etc. Overall, it consists of a number of projects, so the vision is achieved based on concrete projects with their timelines, budgets, goals, etc. It lacks inclusiveness of the general public and local communities – despite the fact everyone may suggest a specific project to implement via the website.</p> <p>Technology: Centralization and digitalization of public registers, ensuring physical and cyber protection.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Os Miñarzos Marine Reserve (ID=409)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes
Main Purpose or Goal	This vision is to create a marine protected area for small-scale fisheries by using a co-management and democratic innovative system
The 'What'	Starting with a fragmented and divided fisheries sector, the main challenge was to construct a common vision of a sustainable future for the MPA and the economic development of the associated coastal communities. More than 10 years after its full implementation, the transformative change that took place since the creation of the MPA not only had repercussions on fishing practices and outcomes (e.g. higher abundance of species and economic revenues), but also on the beliefs and social values of the main fishers, scientists and representatives of the regional administration involved in the Management Body of the MPA. Trust and cooperation, essential elements to successfully govern common pool resources, have been improved since fishers provide data and participate in different monitoring programs. There has also been a notable reduction of conflicts and mistrust between the administration and the fisheries sector, favoring that most decisions concerning fishing activities within the MPA are taken by consensus. Another sign of progress was the collective behavior of local fishers working within the MPA who, after the decision of the regional administration to discontinue financially supporting the surveillance to the area in 2010, continued with the inertia of social norms to comply with the fisheries law, even 2 years after that decision.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Sustainable and holistic wellbeing Democracy Resilience Quality of life Identity Prosperity Equity Justice Recovery
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: the vision refers to how to sustainably manage fishery sources Relational: the vision aims to generate a new way of human-ocean relationship by using a co-management, innovative and democratic governance system
Direct Drivers	Pollution Sea use Climate change

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: sustainability and long-term perspectives is at the core of the new management system, compared to short term and profitability oriented strategy developed in the past</p> <p>Economics: the reserve helped to improve the economic revenues and jobs for coastal communities.</p> <p>Governance: The case of Os Miñarzos also inspired other coastal communities not only in other regions of Spain (namely Catalonia and Andalucia), but also the new fisheries Law in Portugal as well as the Voluntary Guidelines for Securing Sustainable Small-scale Fisheries in the Context of Food Security and Poverty Eradication developed by FAO. All of these initiatives inspired by the Os Miñarzos case have been highly positive to develop new sustainable trajectories, and they are currently in different phases of development and degree of success. More recently, the transformative initiative initiated in Os Miñarzos served as the seed to create a new network of small-scale fishers in Latin America and the Caribbean, Portugal and Spain, involving more than 20 million of fishers(women).</p> <p>Technology: the use of GPS helps to monitor vessels within the reserve.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Winners and losers in a world where the high seas is closed to fishing (ID=359)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	Close the high sea to commercial fishing
The 'What'	Closing the high seas could be catch-neutral while inequality in the distribution of fisheries benefits among the world's maritime countries could be reduced by 50%.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Equity Justice Social wellbeing
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: the vision focuses on the close of the high sea to fishing. We find that closure of the high seas would not lead to losses in aggregate global catch if catches of straddling taxa within EEZs following the closure increase by at least 18%, on average, due to the spillover of biomass from the closed high seas areas. With an 18% increase in the catches of straddling taxa, 120 maritime countries experience net gains in the landed values of their fisheries catches, 65 countries experience net losses and seven countries experience neither gains nor losses. Using the predicted 42% yield increase by White and Costello ¹⁷ , the global catch and landed values increase by 11 million t and US\$13 billion (16% and 15% higher, respectively) per year relative to the status quo. In this scenario, 135 countries experience net gains in landed values, 50 countries experience net losses and seven countries experience neither gains nor losses
Direct Drivers	Sea use Climate change

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: We find that closure of the high seas would not lead to losses in aggregate global catch if catches of straddling taxa within EEZs following the closure increase by at least 18%, on average, due to the spillover of biomass from the closed high seas areas.</p> <p>Economics: Economic concerns centre on the fact that many fisheries exploiting high-seas resources would not be viable without government subsidies and socially, only provide jobs and significant incomes to relatively few.</p> <p>Governance: From a legal standpoint, both fish and fishers of the high seas are the least protected by international agreements¹⁰, leaving those working on high-seas vessels vulnerable to exploitative treatment and unsafe working conditions. The top 10 countries that currently catch the most by value in the high seas, the Small Island Developing States (SIDS), as identified by the UN and the group of ‘Flag of Convenience (FoC) countries’, i.e., those for which 50% or more of the fishing vessels in the fleet are flying the flag of a state that does not match the state of vessel owner control or residence.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Building climate resilience, sustainability and social equity (ID=364)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes. Prellezo, R., Da Rocha, JM, Palomares, L., Sumaila, R., Villasante, S. Nature Ocean Sustainability (in press).
Main Purpose or Goal	This paper uses the scheme to identify global fishing activities that could be reduced because they are biologically negative, economically inefficient, and socially unequitable
The 'What'	We compute the yearly willingness to sequester carbon considering CO2e trading price for 2022 and the social cost of carbon dioxide (SC-CO2), for years 2025, 2030 and 2050. The application of our MBS scheme will result in 0.122 Gt CO2e sequestered or US\$66 billion of potential benefits per year when considering 2050 SC-CO2. The latter also implies that if CO2e trading prices reach the 2050 social cost of carbon, around 75% of the landings worldwide would be more valuable as carbon than as foodstuff in the market.
Broad Values	Equity Justice Social wellbeing
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: the potential gains of an MBS scheme -as the one proposed here- are not only reflected in terms of economic efficiency of the fishing activities. We have shown that it also generates a more equitable distribution of the income obtained from marine resources. Furthermore, this gain is gradual, and at 2022 ETS prices, the effect is higher and more intense in the redistribution of income than at the efficiency level. In summary, it produces a socialisation of the climate costs of fishing and benefits the overall fisheries challenge which is to keep global ocean biomass high enough to keep a profitable fisheries sector, while at the same time increasing resilience which supports other values that we obtain from the seas.
Direct Drivers	Sea use Climate change

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: The paper proposes the internalisation of shadow prices for harvested fishes calculated through their blue carbon content, while economic efficiency is obtained by allowing the trade of CO_{2e} allowances. This scheme provides the global economy with an alternative for the fisheries sector, which grapples with the complexity to find alternatives to reallocate invested capital. It also induces reducing (over)fishing and contributes to build climate resilience and a more equitable distribution of income from the oceans. The internalisation of the climate effect of fisheries (considering only the blue carbon) would imply a 22%-increase of the average ex-vessel prices worldwide if 2050 climate targets are considered.</p> <p>Economics: This paper addresses this issue, showing how the provisions of the PA can be stepped up by using a Market Based Solution (MBS), that is, the opportunity cost of producing one ecosystem service (food provisioning) through its effect on carbon sequestration (climate regulation).</p> <p>Governance: The Paris Agreement adopted by the 2015 United Nations Climate Change Conference (PA) targets limiting global warming to 1.5-2°C relative to the preindustrial level to avoid an irreversible loss in human wellbeing³. Article 6 of the PA establishes provisions for engaging in international cooperation through carbon market mechanisms, to support the achievement of nationally determined contributions. To provide a reference of the scale at which the mechanism could support the PA targets, the European Union (EU) Emissions Trading System (ETS) is used. Set up in 2005, the system is a major EU policy to combat the impacts of climate change, and the world's first major carbon market with around three quarters of global carbon trade¹⁴. This system works by setting up a “cap and trade” mechanism, where a total amount of certain greenhouse gasses is allowed to be emitted each year, while companies receive, buy, and sell emission allowances. However, carbon markets seldom reflect the full social cost of production and therefore, Social Cost of Carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) is also used as an additional reference. SC-CO₂ is defined as the monetized value of the damages to society caused by an incremental tonne of CO₂.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Blue Transformation (FAO) (ID=366)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	Blue Transformation is the vision and the process by which FAO, its Members and partners can use existing and emerging knowledge, tools and practices to secure and maximize the contribution of aquatic (both marine and inland) food systems to food security, nutrition and affordable healthy diets for all.
The 'What'	Blue Transformation is a targeted effort to promote innovative approaches that expand the contribution of aquatic food systems to food security and nutrition and affordable healthy diets. Achieving the objectives of Blue Transformation requires holistic and adaptive approaches that consider the complex interaction between global and local components in food systems and support multi-stakeholder interventions to secure and enhance livelihoods, foster equitable distribution of benefits and provide for an adequate use and conservation of biodiversity and ecosystems.
Broad Values	Social wellbeing Responsibility Equity Justice
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: Blue Transformation is a targeted effort to promote innovative approaches that expand the contribution of aquatic food systems to food security and nutrition and affordable healthy diets. Achieving the objectives of Blue Transformation requires holistic and adaptive approaches that consider the complex interaction between global and local components in food systems and support multi-stakeholder interventions to secure and enhance livelihoods, foster equitable distribution of benefits and provide for an adequate use and conservation of biodiversity and ecosystems. Blue Transformation has three core objectives: -Sustainable aquaculture expansion and intensification – to support global food security targets and satisfy global demand for nutritious aquatic food and equitable distribution of the benefits. -Effective management of all fisheries – to deliver healthy stocks and secure livelihoods. -Upgraded value chains – to ensure the social, economic and environmental viability of aquatic food systems, and secure nutritional outcomes.
Direct Drivers	Sea use Climate change

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: Considering this knowledge, the 2021 COFI Declaration identifies priority areas to further transform fisheries and aquaculture, thus developing a twenty-first century vision for the sector where successes from around the globe are shared and scaled to transform aquatic food systems from a perceived problem to a recognized solution for food and nutrition security and environmental and social well-being.</p> <p>Economics: The prevalence of moderate to severe food insecurity has been rising since 2014, exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Over 800 million people now suffer from hunger and 2.4 billion people have severely limited access to adequate food. As we enter the Decade of Action to deliver the Global Goals, the challenge to feed a growing population without exhausting our natural resources continues to increase. In this context, aquatic food systems are increasingly in the spotlight for their potential to provide a larger proportion of humanity’s nutritious food requirements.</p> <p>Governance: To achieve this objective, FAO and its partners must apply and share effective fisheries management systems that restore ecosystems to a healthy and productive state, while managing exploited resources within ecosystem boundaries. Actions to achieve this objective include building global capacity to regularly collect, analyse and evaluate data that support decision-making and consider trade-offs, particularly in regions with limited data and poor capacity. This objective also strengthens social outcomes, applying actions and initiatives that promote equitable livelihoods, and co-management systems, securing access of small producers to resources and services.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Arca de los Mares (Ark of the seas - Inditex, ZARA) (ID=368)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The aim was to eliminate logistical barriers and intermediaries, as well as packaging and containers. The local product and the promotion of local suppliers are an important pillar of the 360 degrees dining room, but not the only ones. Because the objectives, in addition to healthy and responsible food, cover several aspects, such as the protection and regeneration of the environment, reducing the impact on the climate and natural resources, raising awareness and changing social attitudes, as well as caring for the workers, who are offered eight different menu items every day.
The 'What'	Arca de los Marers also has a space free of single-use plastics. Therefore, single-use plastic bottles and soft drink cans have been eliminated. Treated water is served from the tap and soft drinks are also served in bulk. They have a space free of single-use plastics. Therefore, single-use plastic bottles and soft drink cans have been eliminated. Treated water is served from the tap and soft drinks are also served in bulk. Table cloths have been eliminated, glasses are made of glass, napkin rings of FSC-certified wood, napkins of recycled paper, spoons of compostable materials made from sugar cane.
Broad Values	Social wellbeing Responsibility Equity Justice Community
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: the vision focuses on the need to sustainability use terrestrial and marine resources to significantly reduce the environmental impacts on ecosystems. Because the objectives, in addition to healthy and responsible eating, cover various aspects, such as protecting and regenerating the environment, reducing the impact on the climate and natural resources, raising awareness and changing social attitudes, as well as caring for the employees, who are offered eight different menus every day.
Direct Drivers	Land use Sea use Pollution Climate change Natural resource use and exploitation Invasive species

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: the radical shift towards the use of only local products (70 local marine species) to develop the menus for the employees (1600 only in the city of A Coruña, Spain) of the company. The local product and the promotion of local suppliers are an important pillar of the 360 degrees canteen, but not the only ones.</p> <p>Economics: More than 150 kilos of fresh fish, also zero kilometre, sustainable, purse seine (inshore) and artisanally caught every day. They have a space free of single-use plastics. Therefore, single-use plastic bottles and soft drink cans have been eliminated. Treated water is served from the tap and soft drinks are also served in bulk.</p> <p>Tablecloths have been eliminated, glasses are made of glass, napkin rings of FSC-certified wood, napkins of recycled paper, spoons of compostable materials made from sugar cane.</p> <p>Governance: the vision creates a network with local producers based on fair and just prices based on a participatory process to be involved in the vision.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	One with the Tao (ID=908)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision aims to become one with the Tao, i.e., the great Mother whence everything originates from and that sustains everything.
The 'What'	The Tao gives birth to the then thousand things of nature and She nourishes them and protects them without trying to own them. If you hold on to the Tao or the Mother, you'll suffer no harm. We can understand that merging the mind with the world, in other words meditating and silencing the mind, becoming one with the Tao, leads to a spontaneous self-transformation, to the emergence of virtue within oneself and to developing our full potential as servants of society and nature.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Justice Equality Unity
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: It does not aim at reversing biodiversity loss nor addresses its drivers as we currently understand them. Broadly speaking, it does include statements on how quality of life can be enhanced.
Direct Drivers	This topic is not really covered explicitly, but the vision seems to cover all spectrum of drivers broadly.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<p>Values: It is clear about what needs to be transformed as it speaks of inner transformation. The proposed transformative changes contain references to justice and equality.</p> <p>Economics: This topic is not really covered. However, some references to positive effects of beholding the Tao in one own's life (strength, freedom from harm) are also references to good health.</p> <p>Governance: This topic is not really covered. However, several references to behavioural change can also be seen as norms of a moral nature pertaining to 'structures', e.g. 'behave humbly' or 'don't claim authorship for your actions or virtues'. There is one reference to the dangers of establishing a system.</p>
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	The garden of paradise (ID=911)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision aims to describe the paradise that comes after a judgment where all our acts are revealed and judged.
The 'What'	Quran is full of verses of a symbolic nature, concealing eternal values, speaking about resurrection and paradise. In this vision, elements of nature, and specially a garden, are used to describe a state of bliss where pure joy and satisfaction are experienced as a reward of good deeds.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Divine justice Responsibility Moral norms
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: It does not aim at reversing biodiversity loss nor addresses its drivers as we currently understand them. It does include clear statements on high quality of life in the vision (the description of paradise).
Direct Drivers	This topic is not really covered explicitly, but the vision would seem to cover all spectrum of drivers broadly.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<p>Values: It speaks of inner transformation towards reaching the highest human potential (state of everlasting bliss), but it is less clear what exactly needs to be transformed. The proposed transformative changes contain references to divine justice: the righteous reach the paradise whereas the wicked receive their punishment. It stresses the priority of righteousness and of following the way that God showed to humans. It thus shapes how the followers of Allah see the world, their place within it and what they value the most.</p> <p>Economics: Elements related to food (fruits, wine, vessels, goblets...) are used to emphasize the state of bliss in the vision's description. It is thus a symbolic reference to food. Elements related to water (rain, fountain, rivers) are used to emphasize in the vision's description of paradise. It is a symbolic reference to water.</p> <p>Governance: no explicit reference to governance, but the vision refers to the inner transformation. The righteous perform their vows and feed the indigent for the love of God, without expecting any reward from Him.</p>
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Forests of Kalpataru trees (ID=914)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	Vision of a large-scale redemption whereby the poet-saint Dnyaneshwar asks God that his desire becomes true (boon). In his desire and vision, the wicked become righteous and develop a liking for good deeds.
The 'What'	All beings feel friendly with one another. Evil vanishes and the universe sees the light of one universal religion. At the same time, the desire of all human beings is fulfilled. In the visions, faithful saints arrive on the earth and disseminate blessings and joy. The poet compares these saints with forests of Kalpataru trees (a Kalpataru tree is a wish-fulfilling tree present in the Hindu mythology).
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Justice Good action Happiness Power
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: It does not aim at reversing biodiversity loss nor addresses its drivers as we currently understand them. It includes reference to high quality of life as human beings see their desires fulfilled.
Direct Drivers	This topic is not really covered explicitly, but the vision would seem to cover all spectrum of drivers broadly.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<p>Values: It is clear about the need to transform wickedness into a liking for good deeds. Although there is no explicit reference to justice, one can sense a strong component of brotherhood between human beings that are friendly to each other. The vision has the potential to affect how we see our place in the world as part of a humanity where we are friendly to each other, and we are ever-satisfied. Reference to fulfillment of human desires speaks about good health.</p> <p>Economics: The poet compares these saints with forests of Kalpataru trees (a Kalpataru tree is a wish-fulfilling tree present in the Hindu mythology). He also compares the saints with mines of jewels that grant wishes and with vocal oceans of nectar, meaning that they can spread joy with their voice.</p> <p>Governance: It remains vague in terms of who is doing what, where, why, and how. Except for a 'category' of stakeholders, the saints, who arrive on this Earth to distribute blessings and joy to human beings. This can be interpreted as a call for people to become enlightened to help transform society.</p>
Open coding	
	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)

Vision Id and Name (if available)	Self-realization will save humans and nature (ID=923)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision advocates for self-realization, the common message of all religions, which says that we should get the knowledge about ourselves, who we are and what is the purpose of life. Besides the spiritual goal of self-realization, in this vision there are also concrete everyday goals like favoring handmade products or using the car less.
The 'What'	Through the method Shri Mataji invented (Sahaja Yoga) a living energy called Kundalini is awakened within humans that destroys the negative forces that are acting against them and against nature. This energy is the reflection of the so-called Adi Shakti or Primordial Power, which is like the Mother of the Universe, the Earth and all her creatures.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Self-realization Equality
Specific Values of Nature	The three value domains are present in this vision.
Direct Drivers	This topic is not really covered explicitly.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<p>The vision does not explicitly aim at reversing biodiversity loss, but speaks and addresses some of the main indirect drivers like materialistic and greedy worldviews.</p> <p>Values: Humans can stop the degradation of nature if they get self-realization. Self-realization is the common message of all religions, which say that we should get the knowledge about ourselves, who we are and what is the purpose of life.</p> <p>Economics: Self-realized people will go beyond greed and materialism, will favor handicrafts over industrially produced objects (as it was advocated by Ghandi), will use cars less and walk more, will behave compassionately with other human beings, will spread self-realization. Few mentions to food are included.</p> <p>Governance: Empowering vision focusing on the inner force to fight against what harms us and nature, which is awakened in us through self-realization. The vision is clear about who should do what (get self-realization through Sahaja Yoga) but there are not really differences across stakeholders (all should do the same).</p>
Open coding	
	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Towards a Global Ethic (ID=924)

Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision aims to set up a common set of core values across the world's religions and forms the basis of a global ethics. In these values there are guidelines for human behaviour which are the condition for a sustainable world order.
The 'What'	It declares the interdependence between the different components of the Earth – including humans – and the whole, and commits to responsibility, forgiveness, and a just social and economic order where humankind is a family. Proposes a vision of peoples living peacefully together, of ethnic groups and of religions sharing responsibility for the care of Earth. Signatories commit to a global ethics based on those guidelines and call for increased awareness through prayer and meditation.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Justice Equality Moral principles
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: The vision does not explicitly aim at reversing biodiversity loss, but it specifies how some of the interactions between these components will be changed in the desired state, like for example relations based on mutual respect for life instead of greed or exploitation.
Direct Drivers	This topic is not really covered explicitly. It does not use the word 'biodiversity' but rather nature, ecosystems, or biosphere. However, it is clear that it aims at reversing biodiversity loss and at encouraging its sustainable use while addressing some of the major drivers of degradation. It explains how the vision implies a better quality of life and has a strong focus on equality.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	<p>Values: Common values across the world's religion that are invoked here shape how we see the world and our place in it (interdependence, care for the Earth). Basic religious directives (e.g. You shall not kill) determine what we value and prioritize (respect life).</p> <p>Economics: It is clear about what needs to be transformed: not only unjust economic structures based on greed for example, but also the moral foundations of such structures and the consciousness and the hearts where they lie. Mentions unjust institutions and structures as responsible for current problems like hunger and the need for a more just economic structure. However, economic plans, political programs, legal regulations alone cannot solve current problems and need the moral foundation provided by religions and their set of common values. Some reference to water, oceans, fishing.</p> <p>Governance: It is articulated in several principles and directives. Together with clear explanations, these can help people envision the desired future even if the main focus is on values.</p>
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Multi-Faith Response to the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework (ID=931)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision aims to set up a call to action by a group of religious bodies and faith-based organizations to communicate their desire for strong global action to reverse biodiversity loss.
The 'What'	The vision emerges based on the sacredness of all life and the importance of sacred wisdom of indigenous peoples, spiritual communities, and faith groups, with a commitment to a rights-based approach to conservation. Following the launch of this Call, the Faith and Biodiversity UN Coordination Group was established. It has been signed by 50-60 (depending on source) religious bodies and faith-based organizations. Although it is not very inspiring because it is extracted from a technical document, it is important as it speaks directly to the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Biodiversity Justice Equality Human rights Rights of indigenous peoples
Specific Values of Nature	Relational: The vision is created by a group of religious bodies and faith-based organizations to communicate their desire for strong global action to reverse biodiversity loss. The vision emerges based on the sacredness of all life and the importance of sacred wisdom of indigenous peoples, spiritual communities, and faith groups, with a commitment to a rights-based approach to conservation.
Direct Drivers	Addresses some of the major drivers of biodiversity loss (industrial agriculture, short-term financial profit, etc.)

<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)</p>	<p>Values: the vision is very relevant for indigenous and local communities as well as for national representatives in international conventions.</p> <p>Economics: It briefly mentions the need to address the existing economic systems and to prioritize wellbeing of people and planet over short term financial profit. It is clear in the need to address the overwhelming impact of industrial agriculture, food systems and fossil fuel industries. They believe 'genuine transformative change is needed at all levels to achieve living in harmony with nature and an equitable rights-based nature positive world'. Only one reference to water resources, and one reference to the need for integrated approaches such as One Health Model.</p> <p>Governance: It recognizes that faith groups are diverse and may have specific positions on particular elements of the framework. Demands more details on the implementation mechanisms. Includes reference to certain practices like agroecology or participatory whole of society approach to better implement the Global Biodiversity Framework.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Global Fishing Watch (ID=1015)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No description provided. But information available at: https://globalfishingwatch.org/
Main Purpose or Goal	To create and publicly share knowledge about human activity at sea to enable fair and sustainable use of our ocean.
The 'What'	GFW use cutting-edge technology to turn big data into actionable information. They believe human activity at sea should be common knowledge in order to safeguard the global ocean for the good of all.
Broad Values	Harmony with nature Human well-being. Democracy. Transparency Responsibility Cooperation Ability to tackle complex global challenges
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: the vision aims to improve the monitoring of the ocean and identify illegal and/or non-responsible practices, which are essential to ensure sustainable seafood production and livelihoods.
Direct Drivers	Sea change Climate change Pollution
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	Values: working with real and public data accessible to all improves the way people behave and act, changing the paradigm of sustainable fisheries. Technology: the vision provides open-access data visualizations and analysis tools enable scientific research and drives a transformation in how we manage our ocean. Governance: working with real and public data is helping policy makers to use this information in their decision making processes.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Nuru International (ID=961)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly, though the website was checked for further input. https://nuruinternational.org/about-us/our-story/
Main Purpose or Goal	We envision a future for these communities where young people won't remember a time when their community lived in poverty. Together, we can make that future a reality, and cultivate lasting meaningful choices in the most vulnerable and marginalized communities in the world. Nuru's approach has been to work specifically with smallholder farmers and their families living in extreme poverty in fragile rural areas. We firmly believe that mainstreaming technology in development requires the power of digital currencies, on-farm data, remote sensing, and many other disruptive and appropriate technologies to be embedded in the business models of the farmer organizations we serve.
The 'What'	Nuru's approach of sustainable, locally-led development is based on this philosophy: a strong African woman who possesses the same skill set and knowledge as an international development expert is far more capable of sustainably ending extreme poverty in her country than the expert will ever be. From day one, every Nuru project starts with building local ownership and buy-in. Nuru starts a separate local organization (with its own board) in each country that it operates. Nuru acts as the scaffolding around the local organization. Needs are identified with the community. Programs are co-designed locally. After 5-7 years, Nuru leaves behind a completely self-sustaining impact model owned and operated by empowered local leaders that then expands to additional regions.
Broad Values	Address: hunger, financial shocks, preventable disease and death, especially for mothers and children. Agency Resilience Sustainable livelihoods for vulnerable, marginalized communities Justice Equity
Specific Values of Nature	By inference, the relationship with nature is <i>Instrumental</i> : Nuru works together with farming communities to identify nutritious crops that can also be sold commercially. It then trains farmers in best agronomic practices to ensure higher crop yields and farms that will continue to produce over time to build resilience in both households and communities.
Direct Drivers	Locally-driven farming/agriculture.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	Governance: locally-led and governed cooperatives that replicate when successful.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Ai for Good (ID=1012)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	The link was checked for further information. https://ai4good.org/
Main Purpose or Goal	We use <i>Economic thinking</i> and <i>technology innovation</i> to solve big human challenges, transform institutions, and impact people's lives today.
The 'What'	Ai FOR Good is driving forward technological solutions that measure and advance the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, by bringing together a broad network of interdisciplinary researchers, nonprofits, governments, and corporate actors to identify, prototype, and scale solutions that engender positive social change. The goal is to work with developing nations to design national AI policy frameworks by which they can meet the needs of their populace, equipping them with the tools to increase the communication capacity of their urban and rural communities while being economically competitive on the international stage.
Broad Values	Intelligent cities: harness the potential of emerging technologies to enhance quality of life in cities around the world. Intelligent countries: independent and detailed expertise to accelerate sustainable economic development globally. Innovation Sustainable development Scientific discovery Ethics Innovative health care Workforce diversity Financial inclusion Market efficiency Transparency
Specific Values of Nature	Instrumental: to the extent that nature is mentioned (limited), it is for instrumental reasons. The initiative has formed an SDG catalyst to accelerate purpose-driven startups to set the benchmark for tech-enabled sustainable development. ●
Direct Drivers	Data sets developed provide information on specific issues of nature and societies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Global health data ● World Research Institute (includes flood hazards, water risk, water stress) ● Global Forest Watch (land cover, land use, biodiversity metrics, forest change) ● Humanitarian Data Exchange ● NOAA/Climate governance ● Ocean Tracking Network ● Tracking SDG 16 ● WJP Rule of Law Index ● And others...
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts)	Technological: Using AI to develop datasets, provide tracking and other indicators for natural and social systems. Economic thinking and technology to solve big human challenges, transform institutions, and impact peoples' lives today.
Open coding	
	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Global Deal for Nature—Half Earth, 30 by 30 (ID=300)

Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	To protect 85% of species on the planet by using an evidence-based approach to protect the most biodiversity-rich areas.
The 'What'	The Global Deal for Nature (GDN) is a science-driven plan to save the diversity and abundance of life on Earth. The vision is based on the Half Earth vision to protect and restore 50% of ecosystems by 2050, with “30 by 30” set as a milestone underway. Protecting half of the world’s ecosystems will, according to the researchers, halt loss of biological diversity, contribute to climate stabilization and contribute with necessary services to support quality of life.
Broad Values	Protect biodiversity, halt biodiversity loss Climate stabilization Health and climate services, economic livelihood gains provided by protecting nature. Quality of life, livelihoods
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Instrumental Values (most dominant), ecosystem services for maintaining quality of life and generating livelihoods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Optimize use of land and water ● Provide clean energy ● Sustainable fisheries management ● Circular economy ● Regenerative agriculture Intrinsic: conserve nature for both people and nature <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Protecting ecosystems for purifying water and protecting against climate hazards
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Inspired the Kunming-Montreal protocol, and emphasizes changing key direct drivers as identified by IPBES, targeting transformation by design through area-based conservation and regulation of human activities in which inter-governmental actions and legal approaches play a prominent role. The vision draws on Tallis et al. who found that it is possible to optimize use of land and water by protecting half of the earth, providing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● clean energy, ● sustainable fisheries management, ● circular economy & ● regenerative agriculture.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Technology: technological innovations are mentioned but less elaborated. Governance: creating protected areas for between 30 and 50% of the Earth for biodiversity. Economic: financial innovations, mentioned though less elaborated.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	More Sustainable 2030: Living and Connecting (ID=690)

Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes though the document was also consulted. Oceans and society: feedbacks between ocean and human health SpringerLink
Main Purpose or Goal	The vision aims at transforming the world by changing worldviews on how people interact with nature by enhancing citizen awareness, literacy and engagement, using the One Health approach that links ocean and human health.
The 'What'	The transformation includes fostering an integrated management approach to "marine citizenship and a sense of community relating to healthy oceans, circular economy, a shift towards consumption of nutritionally rich seafood, careful placement of offshore industries and multi-trophic aquaculture, redistribution of power to communities. The vision aims to re-connect communities with the ocean among others through distribution of power and citizen engagement.
Broad Values	Equitable blue economy Localization of decision making Human health (physical, social well-being, mental, spiritual) Engagement Sustainable human-marine environment relationships Awareness through the arts Community
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Relational: highlights relational values, and also presents an integral approach (that includes instrumental, intrinsic, and relational values): Internalized values of ocean health, self-identity, benefits people, nature, and the economy, facilitated by integrated management across sectors
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Pollution: innovations reducing pollutants, minimizing food waste, increased adequate nutrition and energy Exploitation: 'one health' framework, emphasizes human and ocean health, including feedbacks, strong commitment to precautionary approaches allows for integrated decision making, cumulative impact assessment across sectors Species: sharing information on harmful algal blooms
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Economic: circular economy, reduced resource extraction, ecoengineering, renewable energy, offshore aquaculture, food safety, including economic incentives that encourage behavioral changes necessary for achieving desired sustainability outcomes, Demographic: consumption of nutritionally rich seafood by food insecure populations Governance: a shift towards more trusted relationships among stakeholders to enable two-way knowledge exchange, and stronger regulations that simultaneously focus on ocean and human health.
Open coding	Transdisciplinary research and development Use of art, aesthetic benefits of healthy marine environment

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Convention on Biological Diversity (ID=127)

Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No. There were no comments. Needed to consult the website/documents. https://www.cbd.int/convention/
Main Purpose or Goal	"The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) is an international legally-binding treaty with three main goals: conservation of biodiversity; sustainable use of biodiversity; and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from the use of genetic resources."
The 'What'	CBD post-2020 framework implements an action to bring about a transformation in society's relationship with biodiversity and reach the shared vision of living in harmony with nature by 2050. Objectives: conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components, and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources, including appropriate access to genetic resources and by appropriate transfer of relevant technologies, taking into account all rights over those resources and to technologies, and by appropriate funding.
Broad Values	Humans living in harmony with nature. Equity and equitable sharing of benefits, particularly with Indigenous peoples, women, and developing nations. Cooperation. Conservation and sustainable use.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Intrinsic: biodiversity forms the web of life of which we are an integral part and upon which we so fully depend. Understood as diversity or variety, genetic differences, ecosystems, combination of life forms and their interactions with each other. Instrumental: Conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity critically important to food, health, other needs of people and future generations.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Land use: protected areas established. Rehabilitate/restore degraded ecosystems. Exploitation: regulate/manage biological resources to ensure conservation and sustainable use. Promote recovery of threatened species, control associated risks. Invasive species: prevent introduction, control, eradicate alien species that threaten ecosystems, habitats, or species.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Governance: develop/maintain necessary legislation and regulations to protect threatened species and populations. Nations to cooperate to provide financial/other support, incorporate into decision making. Technology: provide/facilitate access for use of technologies relevant to conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, while not damaging the environment.
Open coding	ILK: respect, preserve, and maintain knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous and local communities embodying traditional lifestyles relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity, promote their wider application, encourage equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of such knowledge, innovations, and practices. Research: promote research that contributes to conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, including fostering public education and awareness. Access to genetic resources: Create conditions to facilitate access to genetic resources for environmental sound uses by other parties.
	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (ID=153)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No, needed to consult original document. https://www.cbd.int/gbf/

Main Purpose or Goal	The vision of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework is a world of living in harmony with nature where “by 2050, biodiversity is valued, conserved, restored and wisely used, maintaining ecosystem services, sustaining a healthy planet and delivering benefits essential for all people.”
The 'What'	To take urgent action to halt and reverse biodiversity loss to put nature on a path to recovery for the benefit of people and planet by conserving and sustainably using biodiversity and by ensuring the fair and equitable sharing of benefits from the use of genetic resources, while providing the necessary means of implementation. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework aims to catalyze, enable and galvanize urgent and transformative action by Governments, and subnational and local authorities, with the involvement of all of society, to halt and reverse biodiversity loss, to achieve the outcomes it sets out in its Vision, Mission, Goals and Targets, and thereby contribute to the three objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity and to those of its Protocols.
Broad Values	Biodiversity is fundamental to human well-being, a healthy planet, and economic prosperity for all people, including for living well in balance and in harmony with Mother Earth. Acknowledge different value systems, including nature and nature’s contribution to people. Good quality of life/human wellbeing Living well in balance and harmony with nature (Mother Earth) Rights of nature/Mother Earth Holistic/ecosystem approach Cooperation/collective efforts Human rights/development rights Gender equality, empowerment of women and girls Reduced inequality (equity) Intergenerational equity
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Instrumental: food, medicine, energy, clean air and water, security from natural disasters/nature’s contribution to people. Relational: recreation and cultural inspiration, living well in harmony with nature Intrinsic: supports all systems of life on Earth. Rights of nature/Mother Earth
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Governance: implementation consistent with relevant international obligations, and recognition of Parties’ rights and obligations. Whole of government/society approach.
Open coding	ILK: ensure that the rights, knowledge, including traditional knowledge associated with biodiversity, innovations, worldviews, values and practices of indigenous peoples and local communities are respected, and documented and preserved with their free, prior and informed consent,[4] including through their full and effective participation in decision-making. Implementation based on scientific evidence. Transdisciplinarity needed.

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (ID=150)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes
Main Purpose or Goal	"The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015, provides a shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future. At its heart are the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)..."
The 'What'	<p>We envisage a world free of poverty, hunger, disease and want, where all life can thrive. We envisage a world free of fear and violence. A world with universal literacy. A world with equitable and universal access to quality education at all levels, to health care and social protection, where physical, mental and social well-being are assured. A world where we reaffirm our commitments regarding the human right to safe drinking water and sanitation and where there is improved hygiene; and where food is sufficient, safe, affordable and nutritious. A world where human habitats are safe, resilient and sustainable and where there is universal access to affordable, reliable and sustainable energy.</p> <p>We envisage a world of universal respect for human rights and human dignity, the rule of law, justice, equality and non-discrimination; of respect for race, ethnicity and cultural diversity; and of equal opportunity permitting the full realization of human potential and contributing to shared prosperity. A world which invests in its children and in which every child grows up free from violence and exploitation. A world in which every woman and girl enjoys full gender equality and all legal, social and economic barriers to their empowerment have been removed. A just, equitable, tolerant, open and socially inclusive world in which the needs of the most vulnerable are met.</p> <p>We envisage a world in which every country enjoys sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth and decent work for all. A world in which consumption and production patterns and use of all natural resources – from air to land, from rivers, lakes and aquifers to oceans and seas - are sustainable. One in which democracy, good governance and the rule of law as well as an enabling environment at national and international levels, are essential for sustainable development, including sustained and inclusive economic growth, social development, environmental protection and the eradication of poverty and hunger. One in which development and the application of technology are climate-sensitive, respect biodiversity and are resilient. One in which humanity lives in harmony with nature and in which wildlife and other living species are protected.</p>
Broad Values	<p>Value people, planet, prosperity, peace, partnership. Collaboration. Respect for international law, human rights, right to development. Gender equality and empowerment of women and girls. Empowerment of vulnerable people. End poverty in all forms and dimensions. Inclusive and equitable quality education at all levels. Promotion of physical and mental health and well-being, extended life-expectancy. Shared wealth, reduced inequality. Education for all. Sustainability. Quality of life. Peace and security.</p>

	<p>Inter-cultural understand. Meet current humans' and future generations' needs.</p>
<p>Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i></p>	<p>Instrumental: Conserve and sustainably use oceans and seas, freshwater resources, forests, mountains, and drylands, and protect biodiversity, ecosystems and wildlife. Promote sustainable tourism, tackle water scarcity and water pollution, strengthen cooperation on desertification, dust storms, land degradation, and drought, to promote resilience and disaster risk reduction. Sustainable urban development and management. In these Goals and targets, we are setting out a supremely ambitious and transformational vision. A world in which consumption and production patterns and use of all natural resources – from air to land, from rivers, lakes and aquifers to oceans and seas - are sustainable. Relational: A world in which development and the application of technology are climate-sensitive, respect biodiversity and are resilient. One in which humanity lives in harmony with nature Intrinsic: where wildlife and other living species are protected.</p>
<p>Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Land: sustainable agriculture, pastoralist development Sea: sustainable fisheries. All: Conserve and sustainably use oceans and seas, freshwater resources, forests, mountains, and drylands, and protect biodiversity, ecosystems and wildlife. Promote sustainable tourism, tackle water scarcity and water pollution, strengthen cooperation on desertification, dust storms, land degradation, and drought. SDG Goal 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development. SDG Goal 15. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.</p>
<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Economic: Fundamental changes in production and consumption of goods and services. Strong economic foundations for all nations, including sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth towards prosperity, including shared wealth and addressing income inequality. People-centered economies, youth employment, women's economic empowerment, decent work for all. Eradicating forced labore/human trafficking, end child labor. Increased productive capacities of least-developed countries, productive employment, financial inclusion, sustainable agriculture, pastoralist, and fisheries development, sustainable economic development, universal access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy services, sustainable transport systems, quality and resilient infrastructure.</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	<p>Migrants: positive contribution of migrants for inclusive growth, sustainable development.</p>

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Everland (ID=106)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Mostly, though needed to consult website. https://everland.earth/
Main Purpose or Goal	Everland exists to help people prosper from conserving their forests and wildlife, resulting in climate change mitigation for the benefit of all.
The 'What'	We mobilize transformative investments into forest communities who are on the frontlines stopping deforestation, halting climate change, and safeguarding biodiversity, in order to deliver conservation outcomes at scale, through a voluntary market mechanism called REDD+ (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Degradation), a United Nations-supported approach that enables corporations to finance emissions reductions by halting deforestation in highly threatened landscapes. Focus on forest communities to deliver conservation outcomes at scale with goals to stop deforestation, protect biodiversity, mitigate climate change
Broad Values	Mitigate climate change. End deforestation: conserve forests to benefit larger climate system. Stop deforestation. Protect biodiversity for the benefit of all, protect life on earth. Help communities prosper. Stakeholder engagement.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Instrumental: Help people prosper from conserving their forests and wildlife, resulting in climate change mitigation for the benefit of all. Enable corporations to finance emissions reductions by halting deforestation in highly threatened landscapes.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Land use: stop deforestation to benefit climate change, indirectly addresses agricultural issues. Exploitation: improve access to clean water in local communities.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Economic: support forest communities at the frontlines to deliver conservation outcomes at scale. Voluntary carbon markets, channel finance from corporations to conservation partnerships. Improved access to healthcare in local communities.
Open coding	ILK: recognize that Indigenous peoples and local communities are the most knowledgeable and experienced stewards of nature.

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Commonland (ID=108)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	No, needed to consult website. https://www.commonland.com/
Main Purpose or Goal	Restoring landscapes to create a brighter future on planet Earth. To secure our collective future on planet earth, we need to learn to live in harmony with nature."
The 'What'	We bring people together to restore landscapes and regenerate the Earth: our common land. With our holistic approach to landscape restoration - anyone can work with nature and their local community to restore a landscape at scale. We aim to restore 100 million hectares of the world's degraded landscapes by 2040, together with our partners. Our collective future depends upon our ability to restore the Earth: our common land. Landscape degradation affects us all. From climate change and biodiversity loss, to pollution and food insecurity, it is at the heart of the world's biggest challenges. Involving everyone in the process of landscape restoration is the only way to achieve lasting change. We build bridges between all landscape stakeholders to deliver returns for community, nature, people, and business alike.
Broad Values	Humans living in harmony with nature. Landscape restoration (common land). Holistic. Thriving ecosystems, economies, communities. Community-based participation and collaboration. Regenerative practices. Ecological rehabilitation. Four returns: inspiration (hope and purpose), social (jobs, social connections, education), natural (biodiversity and soil restoration, for resilient landscapes), financial (long-term sustainable income for communities)
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Instrumental: landscape degradation is that the heart of the world's biggest problems, e.g., food insecurity, water scarcity, biodiversity loss, climate change. Rebalance humans' relationship with nature to secure our collective future on planet earth.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Land: facilitate landscape restoration from the ground up. Protect and restore holistic landscapes across the world. Supporting local farmers to adapt to changing climate conditions, creating a resilient and sustainable agricultural sector. Pollution and Land: Landscape degradation affects us all. From climate change and biodiversity loss, to pollution and food insecurity, it is at the heart of the world's biggest challenges.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Economic: Move to an economic model that protects, restores, and strengthens the environment for future generations.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
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Vision Id and Name (if available)	World Organization of United Cities and Local Governments (ID=1077)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes.
Main Purpose or Goal	...is committed to representing, defending, and amplifying the voices of local and regional governments to leave no-one and no place behind. Together we are the sentinels of the hopes, dreams, and aspirations held by individuals in communities around the world — searching for a life in which the ideals of the SDGs are a lived reality.
The 'What'	Through collaboration, dialogue, cooperation, and knowledge-sharing, we as a World Organization walk the walk, working to advance global response and action through groundbreaking commitments and agreements that become common threads that transcend borders and tie communities together, to uplift and empower the local level. Under the “We Care: Pact for the Future”, the UGLG emphasizes the following: “We care about the transformation of our world into one that is driven by communities, develops a harmonic relation between humanity and nature, and is governed through partnerships and proximity.” ... ‘The Power of We is the strength of the municipal movement to break through, ensuring a future for humanity from the local sphere, that guarantees public services and that brings transformation by our communities.’”
Broad Values	Community driven (localization of decision making) Harmony between humans and nature. Partnership Proximity (localization) Fairness Equity Sustainability Human and cultural rights Intergenerational equity, migration, governance renewal.. Ecological and systemic relationship between people and nature. Collaboration/cooperation Dialogue Knowledge-sharing
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Relational: humans living in harmony with nature, ecological/systemic relationship between people and nature.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	No explicit discussion of direct drivers.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Governance: community driven, governed by partnership and proximity. Collective responsibility to make the necessary adjustments and sacrifices to achieve more equitable, fair and sustainable societies.
Open coding	

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Biophilic Cities Network (ID=1084)

Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	
Main Purpose or Goal	Biophilic Cities partners with a network cities, scholars, and advocates from across the globe to build an understanding of the value and contribution of nature in cities to the lives of urban residents.
The 'What'	As a central element of its work, Biophilic Cities facilitates a global network of partner cities working collectively to pursue the vision of a natureful city within their unique and diverse environments and cultures. Network partners are working in concert to conserve and celebrate nature in all its forms and the many important ways in which cities and their inhabitants benefit from the biodiversity and wild urban spaces present in cities. Biophilic Cities acknowledges the importance of daily contact with nature as an element of a meaningful urban life, as well as the ethical responsibility that cities have to conserve global nature as shared habitat for non-human life and people.
Broad Values	Conservation and celebration of nature. Ethical responsibility to conserve nature as shared habitat for non-human life and people. Inclusive
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	Instrumental: benefits of biodiversity and wild urban spaces. Importance of daily contact with nature to create meaningful urban life. Seeks to reverse the negative trends of urban areas and “create healthy, resilient cities and towns for both people and biodiversity. ...People ‘are smarter, happier, less stressed, even more generous, when we have nature around us’. Opportunity to provide healthy food options for local residents facing food insecurity or food deserts. Relational: conserve nature as shared habitat for non-human life and people. Intrinsic/Relational: Nature has the potential to amaze us, stimulate us, and propel us to want to learn more and understand our world more fully. Nature adds a kind of “wonder value” to our lives unlike almost anything else. The qualities of wonder and fascination, the ability to nurture deep personal connection and involvement, and visceral engagement in something larger than and outside oneself, offer the potential for meaning in life few other things can provide. “Our deep, innate, emotional connection to nature connects us all. The need for this nature where we live, work, & play could never be greater.”
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Land/Species: shift urban land use to include biodiversity, nature, gardens, creating healthy, resilient cities and towns for both people and biodiversity.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Governance: global community of partner cities, organizations, and individuals committed to planning and designing cities with abundant nature, where citizens have rich contact with the flourishing natural world as an element of daily life.
Open coding	

VISIONS ADDED TO FILL GAP OF INTRINSIC VALUES IN FIGURE 2.5B

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Ocean Rights

	Source: Harden-Davies, H., Humphries, F., Maloney, M., Wright, G., Gjerde, K., & Vierros, M. (2020). Rights of nature: perspectives for global ocean stewardship. <i>Marine Policy</i> , 122, 104059.
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Gap filling coding done initially here.
Main Purpose or Goal	Legal recognition of the rights of nature.
The 'What'	<p>To develop a new international legally binding instrument for the conservation and sustainable use of marine biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction. Reinforce existing ocean governance norms, inspire new measure to enhance effectiveness and equitability of beyond national jurisdiction agreement, and enable global ocean stewardship.</p> <p>Rights of Nature approaches aim to develop governance systems that preserve ecological integrity and prevent ecosystem disruption, should recognize nature as a rights-bearing <i>subject</i>, rather than an <i>object</i> owned and controlled by humans.</p> <p>Core premise: nature has inherent rights to exist, evolve, and fulfill ecological functions. Assumption: rights of the living world must be respected, human activities must be managed to prevent destruction of nature. Give nature a voice to honor cultural connection, support societal wellbeing, and safeguard ecological integrity.</p> <p>Four defining characteristics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Rights: Nature is a rights-bearing entity. (Two approaches: inherent rights, either w/in jurisdictions and rights of specific ecosystems/living entities. Closely aligned w/ many indigenous philosophies and governance systems that emphasize the interconnectedness of humans and nature.) 2) Connectivity and the primacy of life: All elements of nature, including humans, are interconnected; ensuring the ongoing health of life supporting ecosystems is a societal goal. (Universal truth throughout history. Gaining strength in policy agendas). 3) Reciprocity: Human use of nature entails a concomitant responsibility to respect, restore and regenerate nature by maintaining, for example, environmental quality, ecosystem structure and function, and natural levels of biodiversity. (Humans are in a reciprocal relationship w/ nature, human use/activities are conditional on responsibility to ensure that they stay within ecological limits, living in harmony with nature). 4) Representation and Implementation: Implementation measures are needed to execute human responsibilities; States should not be the only entity to speak for nature. (Voice and representation: assume that humans have obligation to protect the environment and a right to protect nature from harm) <p>Applied here to oceans specifically, but broader implications exist.</p>
Broad Values	<p>Ocean stewardship</p> <p>Equity</p> <p>Realign human governance systems with ecological reality</p> <p>Interconnectedness of all life, including humans and nature (consonant with many Indigenous worldviews)</p> <p>(Bio)diversity</p> <p>Value of all life</p> <p>Nature-centric</p> <p>Holistic</p>

	<p>Rights Connectivity Reciprocity Representation (voice) (of nature)</p>
<p>Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i></p>	<p>Give nature a voice to honor cultural connection, support societal wellbeing, and safeguard ecological integrity.</p> <p>Relational: Revitalized understanding of the value, role, and interconnectedness of all life on Earth. Nature has spiritual value, cultural heritage, scientific importance. Reciprocal relationship between humans and nature, based on responsibility to ensure humans stay within ecological limits.</p> <p>Intrinsic: Nature has intrinsic value (not merely value for humans), is not human property. Intrinsic rights of nature. Value of all life. Nature as a living system.</p> <p>Instrumental: nature has value to humans, too.</p>
<p>Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Ocean (natural resource) use and exploitation (implications for land/freshwater as well). Biodiversity loss. Sea use.</p>
<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Economic, ecological, scientific and cultural value of biodiversity. Governance</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	<p>SW: I suggest adding this vision for its intrinsic value orientation (though not fully there...) as part of snowball sampling for gap filling. Potential forward pathways and specific instances in which action has already been taken are documented. Based on BBJN agreement (Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction agreement)</p>

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	<p>Nature Needs Half / Global Safety Net for Nature</p> <p>Sources: Dinerstein, E., Joshi, A. R., Vynne, C., Lee, A. T., Pharend-Deschênes, F., França, M., ... & Olson, D. (2020). A “Global Safety Net” to reverse biodiversity loss and stabilize Earth’s climate. <i>Science advances</i>, 6(36), eabb2824.</p> <p>Dinerstein, E., Vynne, C., Sala, E., Joshi, A. R., Fernando, S., Lovejoy, T. E., ... & Wikramanayake, E. (2019). A global deal for nature: guiding principles, milestones, and targets. <i>Science advances</i>, 5(4), eaaw2869.</p> <p>Crist, E., Kopnina, H., Cafaro, P., Gray, J., Ripple, W. J., Safina, C., ... & Piccolo, J. J. (2021). Protecting half the planet and transforming human systems are complementary goals. <i>Frontiers in Conservation Science</i>, 91.</p>
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Gap filling. Original sources consulted here.
Main Purpose or Goal	Time-bound, science-driven plan to save the diversity and abundance of life on earth, avoid catastrophic climate change, conserve species, and secure essential ecosystem services by maintaining and restoring at least 50% of the Earth’s land area as intact natural ecosystems, in combination with energy transition measures.
The 'What'	<p>Natural ecosystems are key to maintaining human prosperity inn a warming world. Create a Global Deal for Nature to ensure climate targets are met while preventing species extinctions and the rapid erosion of biodiversity and ecosystem services in the terrestrial, freshwater, and marine realms. Safeguards biodiversity, addresses climate change. The science of conservation biology underpins the GDN and is based on five fundamental goals: (1) represent all native ecosystem types and successional stages across their natural range of variation—or “representation”; (2) maintain viable populations of all native species in natural patterns of abundance and distribution— or “saving species”; (3) maintain ecological function and ecosystem services; (4) maximize carbon sequestration by natural ecosystems; and (5) address environmental change to maintain evolutionary processes and adapt to the impacts of climate change (17).</p> <p>Ensure creation of networks of protected areas that represent the widest array of habitats and, by extension, conserve the widest range of species and their unique adaptations to their environments.</p> <p>Goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity conservation/protection • Mitigate climate change • Reduce threats to ecosystem intactness and persistence of species • Create 50% protected areas <p>Allow humanity to develop a vibrant, low-impact economy and conserve intact ecosystems, all while leaving space for nature. Scale back human economic activity and numbers.</p>
Broad Values	<p>Biodiversity conservation/protection</p> <p>Mitigate climate change</p> <p>Reduce threats to ecosystem intactness and persistence of species</p> <p>Protected areas</p> <p>Linked to insights, rights, voices of Indigenous peoples and their lands</p> <p>Interdependence (climate, biodiversity)</p> <p>Holistic</p>

	<p>Restorative Broad engagement from civil society, public agencies, communities and indigenous peoples Justice for non-human world Social justice Inclusive justice Equity Food security Rights of nature Rewilding Ecodemocracy Earth jurisprudence Indigenous reserves</p>
<p>Specific Values of Nature <u>Instrumental values</u> <u>Intrinsic values</u> <u>Relational values</u></p>	<p>Intrinsic: Intrinsic dominates and is also linked to instrumental values of ecosystem services that serve humanity’s interests. Global protection efforts, conserving viable populations of species, habitats, and connectivity among protected areas (for migration). Applies to land and ocean/water environments. Linked to carbon sequestration, which is enhanced by biodiversity.</p> <p>Instrumental: controlling climate change and ecosystem destruction will enhance human wellbeing, too, and could enhance the wellbeing and rights of Indigenous peoples. Implies a major shift of both human numbers and economic activities and impacts, with wellbeing for all beings implied.</p> <p>Relational: mostly implicit (e.g. w/ respect to indigenous perspectives and approaches).</p>
<p>Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Exploitation of land, sea, fresh waters Natural resource use and exploitation Climate change Biodiversity preservation/restoration: preservation of Earth’s remaining genetic, species, and ecological diversity (as model for designing human life) Invasive species</p>
<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i></p>	<p>Demographic Economic (human economic impacts) Governance: large scale protected areas reinvents human relationships with the non-human world. Technological</p>
<p>Open coding</p>	<p>SW: I suggest combining these three papers with the Global Deal for Nature that’s already included, which seems to be an initiative in one category called Global Deal for Nature that encompasses all of these citations. Key areas of implementation are discussed and possible additional pathways identified.</p>

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Urban Nature for Nature Future Mansur, A. V., McDonald, R. I., Güneralp, B., Kim, H., de Oliveira, J. A. P., Callaghan, C. T., ... & Pereira, H. M. (2022). Nature futures for the urban century: Integrating multiple values into urban management. <i>Environmental Science & Policy</i> , 131, 46-56.
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Gap Filling. Coded original here. 3 visions coded separately.
Main Purpose or Goal	Creating biophilic cities, incorporating biophilic practices into urban planning to meet pressing needs of cities in the 21 st century. Links to CBD goals of humanity living in harmony with nature.
The 'What'	General description: Cities are compact and rewilding in city parks and in areas around the city is promoted. In the (urban) nature for nature future there is more space for natural areas and biodiversity, enabling ecological processes to operate with little to no human intervention. Here, cities are designed to accommodate dynamic natural processes, such as animal dispersal and floodplain connectivity. Urban development is compact with extensively consolidated greenspaces to better protect and safeguard sensitive and endemic species. Natural habitats are protected and there is space for urban forests and wild parks, which are restored and sustained with native species, increasing ecological connectivity. Rivers and lakes are clean, wastewater treatment is effective, and water pollution is prevented from any and all sources. People and policymakers recognize rivers as living systems, especially in the management and restoration of freshwater biodiversity and riparian buffer zones. Rewilding is promoted as a management strategy in large portions of the city parks, where soft management practices are implemented leading to an increase in the complexity of understory vegetation. Ecological corridors connect urban green areas to wider landscapes. Urban dwellers value nature intrinsically and experience wildlife through various activities such as bird watching and walks in the woods. There is education on biodiversity conservation, which in turn contributes to ecosystem protection and restoration. Housing and city infrastructure are designed to function with nature and people are better adapted to deal with environmental externalities such as floods.
Broad Values	Equity Nature is valued for its own sake Biodiversity and natural areas protected Restoration Connectivity Circularity Biodiversity/species protection Cultural relationship/harmony of people and nature Community Localism
Specific Values of Nature <i><u>Instrumental values</u></i> <i><u>Intrinsic values</u></i> <i><u>Relational values</u></i>	Intrinsic: There is a strong effort here to value nature for its own sake and respect its biodiversity, cultural implications. That said... Instrumental: There is also a strong instrumental overtone, valuing nature for what it does for people, though it is less than in the other visions. Relational: Strong relational qualities are also expressed, along with cultural implications, generational learning.

	Overall, this vision tends towards intrinsic, which was its goal, with a secondary emphasis on relationality and instrumentality.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Land use changes Natural resource use/exploitation
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Economic Governance
Open coding	One of three coded.

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Solarpunk Nature for Nature Source: Reeta Rossi (2023): Pathways to Multispecies Cities: Backcasting from Solarpunk stories, Master's Thesis, 60 ECTS, Socio-ecological Resilience for Sustainable Development, Stockholm Resilience Institute, 2023.
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	Yes. Gap filling. Coded from original source here.
Main Purpose or Goal	In general, to highlight the growing awareness of cities being inhabited by multiple species whose needs are entangled. It develops a set of positive scenarios and pathways created to evoke imagination, using Solarpunk stories as input to a backcasting process combining the Nature Futures Framework, climate resilient development, and multispecies sustainability. Here, we code the Nature for Nature vision.
The 'What'	People place high, intrinsic value on nature, not as a tool for humans, valued as high or higher than humans. Fundamental rights are shared with nature. People care for the environment and participate in activities such as environmental monitoring, supporting vulnerable ecosystems, helping wounded animals. Locals are included in the city's decision-making processes, especially re environment. City is located next to a national park, plus the city itself is green. People aspire to build the city to be a habitat for a multitude of species. There is an ecological sanctuary within the city that attracts species that had previously disappeared. Green walls and roofs attract insects and birds while also producing food. Wildlife bridges encourage non-human passages. Biodegradable 3d printing is used to create new habitats. Conserves biodiversity at species level (protect birds, nurturing spaces for wild animals, nesting spaces for birds in skyscrapers). Biorobots that can learn species cultures have been developed and exist in mixed populations with non-robot individuals. Elephants are common sight in city (collaborating w/ humans and given rights). Climate change adaptation is done considering many species, not only humans. Large amount of green spaces in the city contributes to adaptation as well as mitigation by decreasing temperatures and serving as carbon storage. Poaching is a major crime.
Broad Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fundamental rights shared with nature. • Care for the environment and vulnerable ecosystems/species. • Co-management of natural resources and the city. • Conserving biodiversity. • Technology can help build a city that values nature intrinsically. • Planning the city with multiple species in mind.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Strong intrinsic orientation, whereby people place high, intrinsic value on nature which is seen as higher than humans and having fundamental rights. Nature is not a tool for humans.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Climate change, land-use change, natural resource use and exploitation.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Governance.

Open coding	
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	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	Sentient stewards of the sea (Pereira et al., 2023. Marine Policy)
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	We coded directly from source to fill gap in NfN visions.
Main Purpose or Goal	Vision developed as part of a futures thinking process that could use the NFF as a mechanism to bring more transformative energy into how humans conceptualize the high seas and therefore how we aim to govern the ocean. In particular, the role of imagination and creativity in this endeavor is stressed.
The 'What'	A new Law of the Seas Treaty (UNCLOS 2.0) is negotiated. Nature is put center stage. Resources (including technology) are directed towards better understanding nature. UNCLOS 2.0 grants personhood to nature which has equal rights than humans. CBD and jurisdiction transform accordingly. This enables the protection of vast areas of the high seas and also restoration. Human presence in the high seas is severely limited, except for a network of stations that supports restoration and carbon sequestration. A "Convivium" is set up which includes non-human representation. This may be the new governance institution of the sea. An international criminal court focused on ecocide supports the convivium. Protected areas are closely monitored in relation to main threats (pathogens, invasive species) by a network of sensors that assess conditions against ecosystem thresholds to act accordingly. The natural carbon sequestration capacity of the high seas is enhanced.
Broad Values	- Nature first. - Technology helps putting nature center stage. - Legal personhood of nature.
Specific Values of Nature <i>Instrumental values</i> <i>Intrinsic values</i> <i>Relational values</i>	Strong intrinsic orientation deliberately promoted / looked for in this vision.
Direct Drivers <i>land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Sea use. Climate change. Invasive species.
Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) <i>Indirect drivers: include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet).</i>	Governance.
Open coding	